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Analysis of data of the epilepsy registry in the aral region

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Epilepsy is an important social and medical problem. The persistent relevance of this problem is due to the prevalence of the disease in the population, the severity of clinical manifestations, the low effectiveness of known methods of treatment and the high disability of patients. The analysis of the data of the register of epilepsy in the Aral Sea region was carried out.

Keywords: epilepsy, registry, risk factors, types of seizures, diagnosis

Relevance. The problem of epilepsy is one of the most urgent in modern neurology and psychiatry: its prevalence in the general population is 0.5–1% [2, 3]. The prevalence in developed countries is 5.8 people per 100 population, in developing countries - 10.3 people per 1000 population in urban areas and 15.4 people per 1000 population in rural areas [1, 4, 5]. Epilepsy affects the young, socially active part of society and the average age of onset of epilepsy in adult patients is 23 years. These data emphasize the high medical, social and economic significance of the problem of epilepsy in adulthood. The main cause of epilepsy in adulthood is traumatic brain injury, less common causes are cerebrovascular diseases, consequences of neuroinfectious, perinatal pathology, brain tumors, neurocysticercosis, and chronic alcoholism. Modern diagnostics makes it possible to determine whether the patient has real epilepsy or whether seizures are a manifestation of other disorders. For this purpose, instrumental examinations are carried out, which play an important role in the diagnostic determination of the typology of seizures. Significant is the creation of a register of patients with this pathology, the subsequent possibility of data analysis in order to timely detect the disease and correct therapy.

Aim of the study. Analysis of data from the epilepsy register in the Aral region.

Materials and methods. The analysis of the data of the Register in the Aral region was carried out. During the analyzed period, 155 patients with epilepsy were registered at the dispensary. The history of the disease, types of seizures and forms of epilepsy were studied, neurological and somatic statuses were assessed. Clinical and instrumental examination included EEG and MRI.

The average age of the patients at the time of the examination was 43.9 ± 12.5 years (from 18 to 68 years), men - 95 (61.3%), women - 60 (38.7%).

Results. At the time of filling, 6 (4%) patients had no seizures, 21 (13%) patients had between 1-12 seizures per year, and 128 (83%) patients had more than 12 seizures per year. The frequency of seizures at the onset of the disease was observed every day in 3 (2%) patients, 1-6 times a week in 118 (76%), 2-3 times a month in 18 (12%), 7-12 times a year in 13 (8.4%), 3-6 times a year in 1 (1%), and 1-2 times or less per year in 2 (1.3%) patients.

The main etiological factors were neuroinfectious in 73 (47%) cases and brain injuries in 63 (41%) cases, malignant and benign tumors in the cranial cavity - 6 (4%), peri- and neonatal pathologies - 2 (1.3%) and cerebrovascular diseases - 1 (0.6%).

Concomitant pathology was in 128 (83%) patients. There were such pathologies as retinal angiopathy, hypertension, coronary artery disease, exertional angina, cervical and thoracic osteochondrosis, bilateral cochleoneuritis, diffuse toxic goiter, metabolic cardiomyopathy, chronic duodenitis, pancreatitis, chronic gastric and duodenal ulcer, chronic cholecystitis and other pathologies.

The following types of epileptic syndromes were identified: by localization, focal in 131 (84%), generalized in 23 (14.8%) and unclassified in 1 (1%) patient; by etiology, symptomatic in 147 (95%) patients, idiopathic in 7 (4%) and cryptogenic in 1 (1%) patient.

The following types of seizures were identified in the examined patients: simple partial seizures in 28 (18%) patients, complex partial seizures in 18 (12%) patients, secondary generalized seizures in 45 (29%), several types of partial seizures in 28 (18%), absences in 8 (5%), myoclonic in 5 (3.2%), primary generalized tonic-

clonic seizures in 13 (8.4%), primary generalized tonic in 8 (5%) and atonic seizures in 2 (1, 3%) of patients.

Changes in the EEG were noted in 132 (85.2%) patients, in 23 (14.8%) there were no changes in the EEG. In patients, cases of frontotemporal localization prevailed in 42 (27%) and temporal-parietal localization of the epileptiform focus in 40 (25.8%) patients.

As a result of MRI examination of the brain, hydrocephalus was detected in 114 (73.5%) cases, local changes were detected in 31 (20%) patients in the frontotemporal region, in 30 (19.3%) in the parietotemporal region, in 14 (9%) in the fronto-parietal region, in 13 (8.4%) in the parietal region, in 7 (4.5%) in the occipital region, diffuse changes were noted in 3 (2%) patients. The disability group was established in 93 (60%) patients, including epilepsy in 90 (58%) patients. 2 group disability was established in 91 (58.7%) cases, 3 group - in 2 (1.3%).

Conclusions. Thus, the main etiological factors were neuroinfections in 73 (47%) cases and brain injury in 63 (41%) cases. In patients, simple partial seizures were most often observed in 28 (18%) patients, complex partial seizures in 18 (12%), secondary generalized in 45 (29%), several types of partial seizures in 28 (18%) patients. The cases of frontal-temporal localization prevailed in 42 (27%) and temporo-parietal localization of the epileptiform focus in 40 (25.8%) patients. According to the results of the MRI study, local changes were detected in 31 (20%) patients in the frontotemporal region, in 30 (19.3%) in the parietotemporal region.

Comparison of the clinical picture of the attack, the localization of the focus of epileptogenesis according to EEG data and the results of MRI of the brain expands the possibilities of establishing the etiology of the disease.

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Long-term results after microsurgical treatment of lumbar compression radiculopathy

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Objective. To evaluate long-term results after microsurgical treatment of lumbar compression radiculopathy.

Material and methods. A prospective study includes the treatment results of 120 patients with lumbar compression radiculopathy. The main study group consisted of 60 patients (32 men, 28 women), and the average age was 43.2 (from 22 to 65) years. The comparison group also consisted of 60 patients (34 men and 26 women); the mean age was 45.9 (from 19 to 73) years. In the main group, the tubular technique was used, and in the comparison group, the method of discectomy according to Caspar. Patients ranged from minimal disability to bedridden (Oswestry's index ranged from 30% to 98%).

The criteria for an excellent result were: the absence of recurrence within a year after the operation, the complete disappearance of pain in the back and leg immediately after the operation, the absence of functional limitations or the restoration of the minimum degree of disability (Oswestry index 1-20%) within 14 days after the procedure.

A good result meant the absence of recurrence within a year after the operation, the complete disappearance of pain in the back and leg until the end of the rehabilitation period, the absence of functional limitations, the restoration of a minimal or moderate degree of disability (Oswestry index up to 40%) within 14 days after the operation.

A satisfactory result was recorded in cases of relapse in the early period (up to 1.5 months) with minimal hospital and rehabilitation periods while maintaining a pronounced functional limitation for at least 14 days after surgery.

An unsatisfactory result of treatment was recorded by us in patients with relapses of the disease with pain and radicular syndrome and a disabling degree of disability.

Results. Disease relapses were noted in 6 (10%) patients in the comparison group and 4 (6.68%) in the main study group without statistical intergroup differences ($p=0.327$). Of this number of recurrent cases of postoperative course within up to 1 month, 2 (3.33%) patients from each study group were observed, for a period up to 3 months after surgery, relapses were diagnosed in another 2 (3.33%) patients in the comparison group and 1 (1.67%) patient in the main group. Further, up to six months after the operation, the recurrence of the disease developed in 1 (1.9%) case in the comparison group and 1 (1.78%) in the main group of patients. From 6 to 12 months of observation of the long-term period after surgery, no relapses were noted in the main group, while in the comparison group, repeated radiculopathy was diagnosed in 1 (1.9%) patient. In patients with relapses of the disease, the average duration of repeated inpatient treatment was 5.5 ± 1.049 ($m=\pm 0.4$) days in the main group and 8.17 ± 1.47 ($m=\pm 0.6$) days in the comparison group ($p=0.005$).

The category of unsatisfactory outcomes included 4 (6.7%) patients from the comparison group and 1 (1.7%) patient from the main group. In these cases, longer rehabilitation periods were noted, and the development of relapses with the preservation of life restrictions in the postoperative period. The criteria for a satisfactory result were met in the comparison group by 8 (13.3%) patients with a relapse in the early postoperative period with subsequent correction and short-term re-treatment. In the main group, satisfactory results were obtained in 3 (5.0%) patients. In all other cases, during the study period, excellent (43.3% and 60% in the comparison group and the main group, respectively) and good (36.7% and 33.3% in the comparison group and the main group, respectively) results were obtained. There was a statistically significant difference ($p=0.032$) in the proportion of excellent and good treatment outcomes.

Conclusion. The tubular technique of microsurgical treatment of lumbar compression radiculopathy is characterized by a better recovery of the patient's functional status, a decrease in the frequency of relapses and reoperations, and an increase in the proportion of excellent and good results.

Covid-19 in patients with cirrhosis of the liver: clinical aspects and mortality rates. (Review article)

Abdurakhimova D.R., Musabaev E.I., Kasymova R.I.

Annotation. The 2019 Coronavirus Disease Outbreak (COVID-19) caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome Coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2) quickly turned into a global problem. More and more evidence suggest that chronic liver diseases may have an adverse effect on the clinical outcomes of patients with Covid-19. The current review discusses the possible pathogenesis of liver damage associated with Covid-19, biochemical changes in the blood and mortality from Covid-19 in patients with chronic liver diseases and cirrhosis of the liver. Biochemical liver disorders are common in Covid-19 patients with cirrhosis of the liver. Treatment of decompensated events in patients with cirrhosis of the liver without Covid-19 during a pandemic should not be neglected.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, liver, liver cirrhosis, Covid-19.

Introduction.

Since December 2019, COVID-19 has spread rapidly around the world, leading to a major change in global public health. According to WHO, until February 23, 2021, a total of 111,102,016 confirmed cases of the disease and 2,462,911 deaths were registered worldwide. COVID-19 is mostly acute and can recover quickly, but is considered potentially fatal with a total mortality rate of about 3%.

With the exception of respiratory symptoms such as fever, cough and shortness of breath, patients with COVID-19 often develop varying degrees of liver damage. It is noteworthy that patients with COVID-19 with pre-existing liver diseases, especially liver cirrhosis, have a higher frequency of biochemical liver disorders, liver damage and even cases of liver decompensation. On the other hand, cirrhosis of the liver is assumed to be a high-risk concomitant disease for severe COVID-19 due to its inherent immune dysfunction. Decompensated cirrhosis of the liver and acute chronic liver failure are also key risk factors for poor prognosis in patients with COVID-19.

COVID-19 is best described as a multisystem disease caused by SARS-CoV-2, and it can cause acute liver damage or decompensation of pre-existing liver disease. The respiratory tract is considered the main target of SARS-CoV-2 infection, and a small group of infected people become seriously ill and may develop acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) with a potentially fatal outcome.

Due to the rapid spread of COVID-19, there has been considerable concern about the safe management of patients with pre-existing liver diseases. Recently, more and more attention has been paid to the systemic features of the disease involving organs outside the respiratory tract, including the liver and gastrointestinal tract, which indicates that COVID-19 can be considered as a systemic infectious and inflammatory disease.

The mechanism of liver damage in Covid-19 may be multifactorial. SARS-CoV-2 penetrates into liver cells through carboxypeptidase (ACE2) receptors associated with the angiotensin converting enzyme. ACE2 is mainly expressed on cholangiocytes and to a lesser extent on hepatocytes. Both of these cells help in liver regeneration after liver damage. Infection of a population of cholangiocytes and progenitor cells can lead to a decrease in the regenerative capabilities of the liver. Liver damage in COVID-19 may be partially caused by direct damage to cholangiocytes, and deterioration of liver function may occur due to impaired regeneration. [10,11].

Liver function disorders, such as increased GGT, are consistent with the direct cytotoxic effect of SARS-CoV-2 on cholangiocytes. However, the expression of ACE-2 receptors on hepatocytes is minimal, which indicates a significant contribution of indirect causes of liver damage, rather than direct hepatotoxicity. Treatment of severe COVID-19 with antiviral drugs, immunomodulators, antibiotics or adjuvants may also cause hepatotoxicity. [1,2,3].

The attachment of SARS-CoV-2 to the target cell is initiated by interactions between the spike glycoprotein and its related receptor, angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (ACE2). After interaction with the SARS-CoV-2 receptor, S is processed by a type II transmembrane serine protease bound to the plasma membrane,

TMPRSS2, before membrane fusion, which is necessary for the release of viral contents into the cytosol of the host cell. This hypothesis is confirmed by a sharp increase in the viral load of SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNAs in human liver duct organoids within 24 hours after infection. These data demonstrate that the ductal organoids of the human liver are susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 and support reliable replication of the virus. [4,5]. However, damage to hepatocellulars is more common than cholestasis, secondary to damage to cholangiocytes. In our opinion, the damage of the hepatocellular type observed in COVID-19 is probably associated with temporary damage to hepatocytes by non-viral causes and a violation of the ability of liver regeneration by cholangiocyte progenitor cells, which can worsen liver regeneration and lead to further deterioration of liver function. However, with COVID-19 infection, a different mechanism for changing liver function is postulated. Direct cytotoxicity is due to the active replication of the SARS-CoV-2 virus in liver cells and cholangiocytes. The virus binds to target cells via ACE2 receptors; however, normal serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in most patients contradicts this hypothesis. The cytokine storm hypothesis involves immune-mediated damage due to a severe inflammatory reaction after COVID-19 infection. This hypothesis is supported by significantly elevated markers of inflammation, such as C-reactive protein (CRP), serum ferritin, LDH, IL-6 and IL-2.

Postmortem liver biopsy in patients who died from COVID-19 showed only microvesicular steatosis accompanied by hyperactivation of T cells, which suggests that liver damage is most likely mediated by immunity, and not direct cytopathic damage. Due to the fact that most of the patients were on a ventilator and inotropic support, a violation of liver enzymes could be caused by ischemic hepatitis. However, an increase in the level of aspartate and alanine aminotransferase (AST/ALT) exceeds the upper limit of normal, which indicates ischemic or hypoxic liver damage. Another probable cause is drug-induced liver damage [6].

Cirrhosis of the liver as a risk factor for the severity of COVID-19. Patients with cirrhosis of the liver are also at increased risk of decompensation with SARS-CoV-2 infection. Cirrhosis of the liver should be considered as a high-risk

concomitant pathology. The Global Registry shows that mortality is 33% in patients with cirrhosis of the liver with COVID-19 [22]. In patients with cirrhosis of the liver and COVID-19, mortality is higher than in patients with COVID-19 alone [22,16]. The presence of cirrhosis of the liver should be an independent predictor of mortality from COVID-19 (odds ratio = 12.5, P=0.009) [1].

In a study conducted in the United States, risk factors associated with higher mortality in COVID-19 and CLD were alcoholic liver disease, decompensated cirrhosis of the liver and HCC. Other large registries of patients with cirrhosis and COVID-19, such as safe cirrhosis and COVID-Hep.net, reported mortality in 38% of cases, which can reach 70% in Child-Pugh category C [3].

A total of 2,034 adults (average age 49 years, 57.2% of men) participated in the observational studies of Mantovani A. et al. [23]. The overall prevalence of chronic liver diseases at the baseline level was 3%. In individuals with severe COVID-19 disease, corresponding changes in liver enzymes and blood clotting profile were observed, probably due to an innate immune response against the virus, and it was shown that CLD does not affect the severity of COVID-19.

In a combined analysis conducted by Lippi et al., it was found that CLD was not associated with an increase in the likelihood of severe COVID-19 (odds ratio 0.96) or an increase in the likelihood of mortality (or 2.33). Based on the combined results of early COVID-19 data, CLD played a minor role in influencing the patient's progression towards a severe form of the disease. However, newer studies have convincingly proved that the underlying CLD disease had worse results and more severe COVID-19 disease.

Singh et al. [24] studied 250 patients with CLD [42% – with metabolic fatty liver disease and 50 patients with cirrhosis]. These patients had concomitant diseases such as hypertension (68%), diabetes mellitus (48%), chronic kidney disease (CLD, 32%), chronic respiratory diseases (40%) and congestive heart failure (CHF 24%). Control groups corresponding to the propensity were taken, with the exception of CLD and CHF, and it was found that mortality in CLD increased (12% vs. 4%) compared with patients without CLD. The relative risk (RR) of mortality in cirrhosis

of the liver was (RR=4.6) and in CLD (RR=3.0) compared with patients without CLD. Patients had an increased risk of hospitalization in patients with CLD compared to patients without CLD.

In a small study conducted by Qi et al., COVID-19 patients with pre-existing cirrhosis of the liver were included in the analysis (Child-Pugh class A, B and C in 16, 3 and 2 patients, respectively). The majority of patients had compensated cirrhosis of the liver (81.0%), and chronic HBV infection was the most common etiology (57.1%). Concomitant diseases other than cirrhosis were present in the majority of patients (66.7%). There were no significant differences between survivors (n=16) and non-survivors (n=5) regarding the stage of liver cirrhosis. The incidence of respiratory failure and gastrointestinal bleeding was higher in the inanimate than in the survivors, and one patient developed acute chronic liver failure. However, the limitation was a small number of patients.

In a large study by Moon et al. [10], 12,103 patients with cirrhosis and 49 with non-cirrhotic CLD were registered, and death occurred in 12.2% of cases of CLD without cirrhosis, 24% of cases of cirrhosis of the liver CTP-A, 43% of cases of cirrhosis of the liver CTP-B and 63.0% of cases of cirrhosis of the liver CTP-C. The cause of death in patients with cirrhosis of the liver was lung disease COVID-19 in 78.7% of cases, heart-related in 4.3% and liver-related in 12.2%.

Another multicenter study was conducted by Bajaj et al. [21] and included inpatient patients with cirrhosis + COVID-19 (n=37) compared to patients corresponding to age/gender, only with COVID-19 (n=108) and only with cirrhosis (n=127). It was concluded that cirrhosis + COVID-19 had a similar mortality compared to patients with liver cirrhosis alone, but higher than in patients with COVID-19 alone. Mortality was predicted only by the Charlson concomitant Pathology index.

In the study conducted by Sarin et al., 20,228 patients were registered (185 patients with CLD without cirrhosis and 43 with cirrhosis), with concomitant diseases in almost 80%. Fatty liver disease associated with metabolism (113.61%) and viral etiology (26.60%) were common. Forty-three percent of patients with CLD

without cirrhosis had acute liver damage, and 20% of patients with cirrhosis had either acute or chronic liver failure. With decompensated cirrhosis of the liver, liver damage progressed in 57% of patients, while mortality was 43%. In patients with CLD and concomitant diabetes and obesity, the result was worse. The results were similar in Lavarone et al., who registered 50 patients with cirrhosis with COVID-19 and concluded about a high 30-day mortality in these patients and found an assessment of MELD c (European Foundation for the Study of Chronic Liver Failure, Organ Failure and Cirrhosis) CLIF-C and CLIF-OF in as predictors of increased mortality [7].

A systematic review of 73 studies (n=24,299) showed that 3% of patients with COVID-19 suffered from underlying CLD. The presence of CLD was significantly associated with more severe infection and overall mortality. In addition, there was a slight tendency to increase the need for intensive care and invasive mechanical ventilation in patients with CLD [8].

John et al. 88,747 patients tested for COVID-19 in the National Veterans Affairs healthcare system were identified. The following groups were studied: absence of cirrhosis-SARS-CoV-2 negative (C0-S0, n=75,315), absence of cirrhosis-SARS-CoV-2 positive (C0-S1, n=9826); cirrhosis-SARS-CoV-2 negative (C1-S0, n=3301); cirrhosis-SARS-CoV-2 positive (C1-S1, n=305). 30-day mortality and ventilation rates were 5.2% and 3.6% in C1-S0 and 17.1% and 13.0% in C1-S1. Patients with cirrhosis of the liver and a positive test for SARS-CoV-2 were more likely to undergo mechanical ventilation and mortality, the risk was 4.1 times and 3.5 times, respectively. Higher age, decompensation, and a high score of end-stage liver disease (MELD) were predictors of mortality in patients with cirrhosis of the liver and SARS-CoV-2. Cirrhosis of the liver was associated with a 1.7-fold increase in mortality in patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection [9].

Mallett et al. The results of hospitalization of COVID-19 were reported from the database of discharge from the National Hospital of France, including 3207 patients with concomitant cirrhosis of the liver [12]. Comparison of patients with cirrhosis of the liver with all patients without cirrhosis resulted in mortality OR 1.73

(1.59-1.88), which corresponds to our conclusions. Data were presented adjusted or adjusted for 30-day mortality in compensated cirrhosis (0.71; 0.63–0.80) and decompensated cirrhosis (2.21; 1.94–2.51), which emphasizes the importance of determining the severity of cirrhosis in predicting the outcome [12].

Mendizabal et al., published an update on their prospective study of hospitalized patients with COVID-19[13] This reflects an increase in registered mortality compared to their previous data.

Table 1. Outcomes of COVID-19 in patients with cirrhosis of the liver.

Author link	n	Mortality/ results	Comments
Shalimar [14]	26 cirrhotic diseases	11/26 (42,3%) died	Need for artificial lung ventilation independently predicted mortality (hazard ratio 13.68)
Sarin [15]	3 cirrhosis of the liver against 185 CLD - cirrhosis is not present	7/43 (16.3%) cirrhosis against 5/185 (2.7%) CLD- cirrhosis is not present	Almost twice as high mortality in decompensated cirrhosis (compared with compensated), a Child-Turcott Pugh score of 9 or more when presented predicted high mortality, OR 0.94, OR = 19.2 (95 CI 2.3–163.3).
Iavaron [16]	50 cirrhotic liver diseases	30-day mortality was 34% (n = 17)	Higher mortality in patients with respiratory insufficiency and in patients with impaired liver function.
John [17]	305 Cirrhotic diseases	55 (18%)	Higher age, decompensation and a high MELD score were predictors of mortality.
Moon [18]	03 cirrhotic diseases, 49 non-cirrhotic CLD	Mortality was 12.2% of patients with CLD without cirrhosis, 23.9% with cirrhosis of the liver class A according to Child-Pugh, 43.3% with cirrhosis of the liver	Cirrhosis of the liver of class B and C according to Child-Pugh remained associated with death after adjustment for baseline characteristics.

		class B according to Child-Pugh and 63.0% with cirrhosis of the liver class C according to Child-Pugh.	
Kim [19]	867 patients (including 134 compensated and 93 decompensated cirrhosis of the liver).	9/134 (14.1%) compensated, 38/93 (40.8%) decompensated, 9/22 (40.9%) patients with hepatocellular carcinoma.	Alcohol-related liver diseases, decompensated liver cirrhosis and HCC predict higher overall mortality.
Margot [20]	386 cirrhosis, 359 without cirrhosis.	Mortality was 8% in patients without cirrhosis of the liver, 32% in patients with cirrhosis of the liver.	Mortality is 19%, 35% and 51% and class A, B and C on the Child-Pugh scale, respectively.

Sarin and others., studied acute liver injury (ALI) and its effect on outcomes in patients with non-cirrhotic chronic liver disease and cirrhosis. The authors defined ALI as any of the following indicators: the level of total bilirubin ≥ 3 mg /dl, an acute increase in ALT, AST, SAP, gamma-glutamyltranspeptidase 2 times higher than the upper limit of normal and the international normalized ratio of prothrombin time ≥ 1.5 with previously normal liver parameters. The study included 228 patients; 185 were diagnosed with CLL without cirrhosis of the liver, and 43 suffered from cirrhosis of the liver. A Child-Pugh score of 9 or more at presentation predicted mortality (area under the curve 0.94, sensitivity 85.7% and specificity 94.4%, risk ratio [HR] 19.2 [95 CI 2.3–163.3], $P < 0.001$). Liver damage progressed in 57% of patients with decompensated cirrhosis of the liver, and 43% died. An increase in the level of bilirubin and the AST/ALT ratio predicted mortality in patients with cirrhosis of the liver [15].

Marjot and co-authors compared 386 patients with cirrhosis of the liver and 359 without it and COVID-19 (data from two international registries). The authors compared these data with patients without CLD with COVID-19 from the UK hospital network. Mortality was 8% in individuals without cirrhosis compared to 32% in patients with cirrhosis. Mortality increased with the severity of Child-

Turcott-Pugh disease; 19%, 35% and 51% in patients with classes A, B and C, respectively. Higher age, the presence of cirrhosis of the liver (greater risk in CTP B or C) and alcohol-related liver diseases were risk factors for mortality [20].

Mortality in patients with COVID-19 and cirrhosis of the liver is mainly due to the severity of liver disease. The International Registry showed that 47 patients out of 152 died. In the group of non-survivors, there was a significantly high prevalence of cirrhosis (compared with the absence of cirrhosis) and decompensated cirrhosis (class of children B or C 25.7% in survivors).

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Therapeutic and tactical aspects in the development of psych emotional disorders in perinatal women against the background of infection with COVID-19

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Objective: to develop therapeutic and tactical aspects in developing psychoemotional disorders in pregnant women and young mothers against the background of infection with COVID-19.

Material and methods. The study was based on the results of the examination and treatment of 3080 pregnant women and young mothers infected with SARS-CoV-2 during the COVID-19 pandemic in the maternity ward of the Zangiota-1 Republican Specialized Infectious Diseases Hospital from December 2020 to January 01, 2022. The severity of psychoemotional disorders was identified and assessed according to the GAD-7 anxiety disorder rating scale, the IES-6 post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) rating scale, and the PHQ-9 depressive syndrome rating scale. Identification of combined psychoemotional pathology was performed using a special combined scale PHQ-ADS, which is the sum of scores from the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 questionnaires (the maximum score is 48, and the combination of PTSD, anxiety and depression manifests itself at 20 or more points). The depressive syndrome was characterized by tearfulness, a sense of hopelessness, mild excitability or psychomotor retardation, and recurrent thoughts of death. Anxiety disorders were manifested by fear of illness, fussiness, constant nervousness, trembling and muscle tension. Patients complained of foreboding, difficulty concentrating, headaches, and inability to relax. PTSD was associated with experiencing the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on one's health, the death of a loved one or loved one from COVID-19. Women with PTSD noted insomnia and high anxiety levels,

experienced a feeling of mild excitability, became irritable, and agitated with a sense of physical discomfort. To build therapeutic and tactical aspects, it was necessary to identify the most sensitive and specific scales and questionnaires, based on which it was possible to differentiate one or another type of psychoemotional disorders, as well as to identify mixed forms of psycho-pathology in pregnant women and childbirth with COVID-19 pneumonia during hospitalization and after recovery from the underlying disease. We have made an optimal calculation of the criteria, taking into account the prevalence of the disease and the rates of false and true positive and negative results.

Results. Analysis of the results of the survey on the IES-6 scale in our sample of patients showed that the sensitivity of the IES-6 associated with an index of 2 or more was 83.14%, and the specificity of the method was 98.04% (95% CI was 96.6-99.0; $p < 0.001$). It follows from the literature data that the optimal criterion for diagnosing anxiety disorders in COVID-19 is the result of an assessment on the GAD-7 scale with a score of 5 or more points. According to our data, the sensitivity associated with this criterion is 77.79%, and the specificity is 95.92% (95% CI was 76.1-79.4, $p < 0.001$). The PHQ-9 scale was used to identify and track the dynamics of the progression or disappearance of clinical signs of depressive states. At the same time, the optimal criterion for detecting depression in COVID-19 was ten or more points. According to our data, the sensitivity associated with this criterion is 94.33%, and the specificity is 89.4% (95% CI was 86.7-91.7, $p < 0.001$).

Therapeutic and tactical aspects in the development of psychoemotional disorders in perinatal women were focused on providing a beneficial effect on the course of pregnancy and childbirth, reducing the frequency of threats of interruption, gestosis, weakness of labour, untimely discharge of amniotic fluid, etc.

Drugs complemented psychotherapy.

- metabolite therapy (the first complex - thiamine pyrophosphate, riboflavin mononucleotide, calcium pantothenate, lipoic acid, alpha-tocopherol; the second complex - pyridoxal phosphate, folic acid, cyanocobalamin, calcium glycerophosphate, potassium orotate, glutamic acid, calcium pangamate), which has

a beneficial effect on the psychoemotional state of pregnant women and leads to a decrease in the number of pathological courses of childbirth;

- differentiated psychotherapy includes sedative and antioxidant therapy, "metabolic drugs, permanent tocolytic therapy, physiotherapy courses, and delivery in a specialized centre.

For correcting psychoemotional disorders, herbal preparations that do not have side effects are considered. One of these drugs is common valerian, anti-anxiety complex Phyto therapy that has a mild hypnotic effect, relieves insomnia caused by anxiety, and has a vegetotropic effect with a uniform impact on mental and somatic symptoms of anxiety. An herbal sedative helps relieve stress symptoms (anxiety, irritability and emotional tension).

Cognitive-behavioural group therapy has shown promising results in relieving perinatal anxiety by targeting uncertainty intolerance and adapting existing strategies to address the concern and psychological impact of COVID-19. This intervention in pregnant women during the COVID-19 pandemic can increase this population's stress levels and sustainability.

Eight consecutive weekly sessions of 1.5 to 2 hours with trained psychologists with a master's degree in psychological treatment.

The program consists of 8 lessons with the following content:

- (1) psychoeducation: what is stress, its characteristics, how to identify stressors, how to respond to them and what their consequences are;
- (2) deactivation strategies (thematic imagination and diaphragmatic breathing);
- (3) cognitive restructuring: cognitive distortions;
- (4) cognitive restructuring: irrational beliefs;
- (5) alternative ways to control your thoughts: self-study and time management;
- (6) social skills training: self-confidence, fundamental rights to self-confidence, the ability to say "no" and demand behaviour change;
- (7) the link between anger and stress: emotional self-control;
- (8) optimism and sense of humour.

Each intervention had the same structure and guidelines for content standardization.

At the start of the session, participants received an email with a link to join the virtual session, documents to work on during the session, a behavioural self-report, and tasks to work on at home that week related to the topic. Session.

In addition, all pregnant women and women in labour are encouraged to participate in sessions with various activities such as: talking about their experiences, expressing difficulties about tasks between sessions, role-playing, etc. Those who complete the study show clinically significant improvements in anxiety and depression and a substantial increase in mindfulness.

Women most vulnerable to mental health during the pandemic were women in the postpartum period with miscarriages or experiencing intimate partner violence.

A program to reduce stress, anxiety, and fear of childbirth in pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 includes:

- integration of mental health care and e-health
- the observed social and cognitive mechanisms in this study are adjustable and can be used in the development of evidence-based interventions to improve the mental health of pregnant women
- early social support and identification of the difficulties of pregnant women during a pandemic are recommended to protect their mental health.
- Pregnant women should have easy access to psychosocial support and obstetric counselling during the pandemic

Conclusion. Based on our data on the sensitivity and specificity of the most commonly used questionnaire scales, in identifying and assessing the dynamics of PTSD, anxiety and depression, it is necessary to use the IES-6, GAD-7 and PHQ-9 scales. Diagnostic, therapeutic, and tactical aspects of managing pregnant women and women in labour with COVID-19 and psychoemotional disorders include the use of specialized questionnaire scales and a cognitive behavioural therapy program combined with sedative and metabolic drugs. They can reduce the incidence of perinatal complications and shorten the rehabilitation period.

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Transcranial diplography as a component of a comprehensive assessment of brain vessel changes in children aged 7-18 years suffering with type 1 diabetes.

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Key words: transcranial diplography, brain, cerebrovascular disorders, diabetes mellitus.

Introduction: This thesis describes the transcranial diplography of intracranial cerebral vessels in children aged 7-18 years with type 1 diabetes mellitus. The processes of formation of cerebrovascular disorders with a tendency to aggravation are detected already at the early stages of the disease, which in turn reduces the quality of human life.

Currently, in type 1 diabetes mellitus, the likelihood of developing acute and chronic disorders of cerebral circulation has increased by 2-6 times.

Purpose of the study: Depending on the age groups, to determine cerebrovascular changes in children with type 1 diabetes mellitus.

Materials and methods of research: 43 patients aged 7-18 years who are in the stage of compensation and sub compensation of carbohydrate metabolism were examined.

The duration of the disease varied from 1 to 12 years.

The subjects were divided into two groups according to the classification of N.P. Gundobin: group 1 children aged 7-11 years (n=20); group 2 children aged 12-18 years (n=23).

The changes were most pronounced in PMA and PMA. The anterior cerebral artery supplies blood to the medial sections of the frontal and parts of the parietal lobes of the brain, as well as the anterior and middle sections of the corpus callosum, the anterior sections of the subcortex and hypothalamus.

The internal branches of the PCA supply blood to the upper midbrain, hippocampus, thalamus, and most of the hypothalamus. Thus, with stenosis in the ACA and PCA basin, neurological and neuropsychological symptoms appear.

Conclusions: The results of the Doppler study showed that the average blood flow velocity was reduced in children in 2 groups. In the first group, the indicators of the middle cerebral artery (MCA) {71.1 (63.0-80.2) cm/s;} and the posterior cerebral artery (PCA) {42.9 (3.2-44.7) cm/s; s., in the second group of the middle cerebral artery (MCA) 79.4 (76.8-82.5) cm / s., and the posterior cerebral artery (PCA) 46.5 (44.9-48.0) cm / s. With. The parameters of the anterior cerebral artery (ACA) and basilar artery (BA) did not differ from the norm.

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The significance of premorbid factors in development of affective-respiratory paroxysm in children

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One of the most frequently observed non-epileptic paroxysmal disorders in initially healthy young children is affective-respiratory attacks (ARP), manifested by involuntary breath holding with a short-term impairment of consciousness, breathing, and motor activity in response to exogenous irritating factors, such as pain, fear and etc.

The aim of the study was to study the features of the premorbid background and the most significant predictors of the development of ARP in young children.

Materials and methods. We examined 103 children with affective-respiratory paroxysms aged from 3 months to 3 years who were on inpatient and outpatient treatment at the clinic of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute in the period 2019-2022. They formed the main group. The control group consisted of 20 “conditionally healthy” children. Children of the control group were examined by a pediatrician as part of a standard examination during the observation periods at the stage of outpatient care.

Results. For the purpose of a more detailed study of the factors of the premorbid background in the formation of affective respiratory paroxysms in children, an analysis of the perinatal period (ante-, intra- and postnatal period) was carried out.

An analysis of the antenatal period allows us to conclude that pregnancy in women in 85% of cases proceeded against the background of genital and extragenital pathology. The most common pathologies were a history of miscarriage (35%), toxicosis (56%), threatened miscarriage (25%), anemia (35%), and infectious diseases of the mother during pregnancy (28%).

The analysis of individual medical records of the examined children made it possible to identify retrospective clinical conditions in children: 44 children had a satisfactory condition at birth, 51 children had a moderate condition at birth, and 5 patients had a serious condition. According to the data obtained on perinatal risk factors in this

case, 85% had perinatal damage to the CNS of hypoxic origin (in the form of cerebral excitability syndrome, cerebral depression syndrome, motor dystonia syndrome, vegetative-visceral disorders syndrome and liquor-vascular distension syndrome), in 25 % had intrauterine dystrophy (hypotrophy), 28% had perinatal (intrauterine) infection, and 8% had jaundice up to 1 month.

As a result of our research, concomitant somatic pathology was registered in 90.2% of ARP children. The most frequently observed pathology of the respiratory system, the pathology of the cardiovascular system and the gastrointestinal tract. Diseases of the respiratory and ENT organs were detected in 48.5% of patients, among which community-acquired bronchopneumonia (37.6% of patients) and acute rhinosinusitis (11.9% of patients) were most often recorded. Analysis of the results of the study showed that out of 23.8% of patients with confirmed pathology of the cardiovascular system, sinus node dysfunction was the most common - sinus tachy- and bradyarrhythmia's in 11.5% of patients, transient atrioventricular (AV) block I degree and (AV) II-degree blockade was detected equally often in 12.4% of cases in children of the main groups. Among diseases of the gastrointestinal tract in patients with ARP, acute and chronic gastroduodenitis (35.6%), biliary dyskinesia (15.4%) and dysbacteriosis (56.7%) were most often detected. The combination of several pathologies was more often noted in the main group of children and amounted to 66.8%, while in the control group, the combined pathology was noted significantly less frequently and amounted to 5% ($p < 0.05$). In children of the first year of life, diseases of the respiratory organs ($p < 0.05$) and diseases of the gastrointestinal tract ($p < 0.05$) were significantly more often detected. The second place was occupied by diseases caused by nutrition and metabolism, which in turn is associated with inadequate use of various nutrient mixtures by mothers.

Conclusion. The most significant predictors and premorbid backgrounds for the development of ARP in young children are perinatal CNS lesions and the presence of concomitant somatic pathologies.

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Роль Витамина D для женщин репродуктивного возраста.

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Summary.

Vitamin D deficiency is a worldwide problem. The lack of this vitamin for women of reproductive age is of no small importance. So, with hypovitaminosis D, the frequency of such obstetric pathologies as recurrent miscarriage, placental insufficiency, gestational diabetes, preeclampsia, osteoporosis and bacterial vaginosis increases significantly. Gynecological diseases such as ovarian failure are also increasing.

Резюме.

Дефицит витамина D является мировой проблемой. Немаловажное значение имеет недостаток этого витамина для женщин репродуктивного возраста. Так при гиповитаминозе D, в разы увеличивается частота таких акушерских патологий, как привычное невынашивание беременности, плацентарная недостаточность, гестационный диабет, преэклампсия, остеопороз и бак вагиноз. Также возрастает такие гинекологические заболевания как яичниковая недостаточность.

Резюме.

Витамин D етишмовчилиги дуневий муаммоларга киради. Бу витамин етишмовчилиги репродуктив ешдаги аеллар учун хам жуда ахамиятлидир. Бу витамин камлигида акушерлик асоратлар бир неча бор купрок учрайди. Буларга хомилани кутара олмаслик, плацентар етишмовчилик, гестацион диабет, преэклампсия, остеопороз ва бак вагинозлар киради. Бундай танкислик тухумдон етишмовчилиги каби гинекологик касалликларнинг купайишига хам олиб келади.

Обзор.

Дефицит витамина D является настоящей пандемией в современном мире [1]. Недостаточность витамина D, определяемая уровнем 25[ОН]D равна

или меньше 30 нг/мл, распространена глобально, при этом частота регистрации данного состояния среди населения России составляет свыше 90% [2]. Основную группу риска по развитию дефицита витамина D составляют лица старческого возраста, а также беременные (в особенности при наличии нарушений жирового обмена, гестационного сахарного диабета и инфекционной патологии), которым не проводилась медикаментозная коррекция витаминного статуса. Во многих странах у женщин репродуктивного возраста, беременных и кормящих матерей, имеется высокая распространенность дефицита витамина D, который часто сопровождается негативными последствиями для женщины, плода и новорожденных детей. Материнский дефицит витамина D во время беременности был зафиксирован в ряде исследований. К примеру, 18% беременных женщин в Великобритании, 25% в ОАЭ, 80% в Иране, 42% в северной Индии, 61% в Новой Зеландии имеют уровень концентрации 25[ОН]D ниже 25 нмоль/л. Эти показатели вызывают настороженность. Ведь дети вступают в мир уже с дефицитом витамина D, которая начинается еще в утробе матери [7].

В свете достижений последних лет, доказана роль витамина D также в регуляции репродуктивной функции. Являясь стероидным гормоном, данный витамин необходим для обеспечения широкого спектра физиологических процессов. В связи с чем, его еще называют D –гормоном. В тканях репродуктивных органов: яичниках, матке, плаценте и гипофизе – обнаружены ядерные рецепторы витамина D и 1 α -гидроксилазы [5]. В связи с этим очевидна ассоциация роли витамина D с состоянием репродуктивного здоровья женщин, течением беременности и родов [3].

На фоне дефицита витамина D во время беременности возрастает частота преждевременных родов, аномалий сократительной деятельности матки. Кесарево сечение производится 4 раза чаще, по сравнению с таковым у беременных с нормальным уровнем витамина D. Он также участвует в программировании развития плода и новорожденного. Уровень витамина D у беременных имеет прямую связь с массой тела ребёнка при рождении и

окружностью головки плода. Гиповитаминоз D матери оказывает отрицательное влияние на развитие костной ткани и врожденный иммунитет плода, что имеет большое значение для дальнейшего развития ребенка и способствует к формированию хронизации заболеваний [8]. При снижении уровня витамина D менее 50 нмоль/л регистрируются ряд осложнений во время беременности (угроза преждевременных родов, плацентарная недостаточность, прерывание беременности, преэклампсия, формируется гестационный диабет [5].

Дефицит витамина D связывают также с развитием бактериального вагиноза во время беременности. Бактериальный вагиноз (БВ) является распространенной рецидивирующей вагинальной инфекцией у женщин репродуктивного возраста, наиболее частой в первом триместре беременности. Проведенное исследование установило коррелятивную связь БВ с дефицитом витамина D. По мнению авторов, назначение витамина D будет эффективно в профилактике симптомов и побочных эффектов БВ [11].

Как известно, кальций плохо всасывается при недостаточности витамина D. При его дефиците до 70% кальция остается не усвоенным. У беременных имеется достаточно широкий резерв компенсаторно - приспособительных реакций организма для поддержания кальций - фосфорного гомеостаза [4]. Так, при нормальной обеспеченности витамином D организм легко адаптируется к недостатку кальция во время беременности, благодаря активизации его всасывания в кишечнике. Однако, дефицит витамина D и резкий дефицит кальция в пище могут стать причиной изменений костно-минерального метаболизма в процессе гестации и привести к снижению плотности костной ткани и развитию остеопенического синдрома беременных [1,2].

Восполнение дефицита витамина D имеет очень широкие перспективы для оптимизации состояния здоровья женщин и детей и, может быть, одной из наиболее важных профилактических программ здравоохранения. Так, в 2017 году был проведен метаанализ 24 рандомизированных контролируемых и

наблюдательных исследований, чтобы ответить на 2 вопроса: 1). Есть ли связь между низким уровнем материнского 25-гидроксивитамина D (25-OHD) и повышенным риском преждевременных родов? 2). Может ли прием витамина D во время беременности снизить риск преждевременных родов? [10].

У беременных женщин была исследована взаимосвязь между концентрацией 25-гидроксивитамина D в материнской сыворотке и риском последующего выкидыша. Выявлен риск выкидыша в первом триместре беременности при дефиците витамина D, но при высоких концентрациях витамина D (больше 20 нг/мл) выкидышей не наблюдалось. Недостаточность 25-OHD у матери была связана также с повышенным риском преждевременных родов. Благоприятные результаты были получены при коррекции дефицита витамина D у женщин с выкидышами в анамнезе и преждевременных родов. Эти данные подтверждают целесообразность приема витамина D в период прегравидарной подготовке для профилактики выкидышей и преждевременных родов [6,9].

Таким образом, трудно переоценить роль витамина D в репродуктивном возрасте. Данное обстоятельство диктует необходимость включения определения уровня витамина D при обследовании и лечении женщин с бесплодием, нарушением менструальной функции и отягощенным акушерским анамнезом. Особое внимание необходимо уделять женщинам с яичниковой недостаточностью, привычным невынашиванием беременности и остеопорозом.

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Клинические особенности когнитивных нарушений у больных рассеянным склерозом и цереброваскулярной патологией

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Рассеянный склероз (РС) является одной из сложных и социально значимых проблем современной неврологии, что в первую очередь определяется его распространенностью, устойчивым повышением заболеваемости, непредсказуемостью течения, поражением в основном лиц молодого, трудоспособного возраста и частой инвалидизацией.

Несмотря на активное изучение, РС продолжает оставаться проблемой со многими нерешенными вопросами. Это касается не только происхождения и сущности болезни, но и ее клиники, которая, казалось бы, изучена с достаточной полнотой.

Когнитивные нарушения при РС отмечены многими исследователями. Тем не менее, сведения об их частоте, степени выраженности в клинической картине заболевания противоречивы. В отечественной литературе отсутствуют комплексные исследования, посвященные качественному и количественному нейропсихологическому анализу когнитивных расстройств. Не выработано единое мнение о факторах, влияющих на развитие когнитивной дисфункции при РС.

Когнитивные нарушения (КН) у больных рассеянным склерозом (РС) являются скрытыми для клиницистов, в связи с этим не диагностируются и не учитываются в оценивающих шкалах, таких как EDSS. Выявляются уже на стадии клинически изолированного синдрома. Применение лекарственных препаратов при РС, помогают увеличить продолжительность жизни пациентов, в связи с чем возрастают риски развития сосудистых заболеваний головного мозга.

Цель. Изучить клинические особенности КН у больных РС с цереброваскулярной патологией (ЦВП).

Материалы и методы. В 1-ю группу вошли 30 пациентов (18 женщин и 12 мужчин) с диагнозом РС по критериям McDonald (2017 й) с хронической ЦВП. Ремитирующий тип течения РС (PPC) был у 22 пациентов, вторично прогрессирующий (ВППС) — у 18, возраст больных составлял от 40 до 64 лет; продолжительность РС — от 5 до 18 лет. Степень инвалидизации по шкале EDSS — от 2 до 6,5 балла. Во 2-ю (контрольную) группу включили 25 больных РС (16 женщин и 9 мужчины) в возрасте от 45 до 65 лет, не имевших ЦВП. Длительность РС во 2-й группе составляла от 4 до 16 лет, тяжесть функциональных нарушений — от 1,5 до 6 баллов. PPC был у 20 больных, ВППС — у 5. У всех пациентов определяли психический статус (шкала MMSE), уровень депрессии (шкала Бека), тревожности (шкала Спилбергера-Ханина), памяти (тест Рисование часов), внимания (проба Бурдона), применяли также батарею тестов лобной дисфункции.

Результаты. У больных РС в обеих группах выявлены тревожно-депрессивные расстройства и КН. Общая оценка по шкале MMSE оказалась достоверно ниже у больных РС с ЦВП, чем в контрольной группе ($p < 0,005$). У пациентов 1-й группы уровень тревожности был выше, депрессивные расстройства чаще (легкой и умеренной степени в 59% случаев против 37%). КН проявлялись: в увеличении времени выполнения заданий (85% против 70%), быстрой истощаемостью (78% против 64%), нарушением запоминания (73% против 62%) и снижением объема кратковременной памяти (75% против 58%). В 61 % случаев регистрировались признаки дисфункции лобных отделов мозга (против 32% у больных 2-й группы), умеренные КН наблюдались у 61% (против 49%). Деменция наблюдалась у 12% больных РС с ЦВП. Наибольшее проявление КН выявили при ВППС и ЦВП с длительностью заболевания более 10 лет ($EDSS > 3,5$ балла) у пациентов старше 60 лет. У больных РС с ЦВП обнаружили также выраженную эмоциональную лабильность.

Вывод. Когнитивные нарушения при РС и ЦВП имеют клинические особенности и характеризуются неблагоприятным вариантом течения.

Значения показателей КН при ВПТ коррелируют со степенью инвалидизации, возрастом пациентов, длительностью течения РС.

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Особенности клинико-неврологических нарушений у детей с посттравматической энцефалопатией

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В работе приведены результаты собственных исследований по изучению клинико-неврологических особенностей и состояние вегетативной системы у детей посттравматической энцефалопатией перенесших ЧМТ лёгкой и средне – тяжёлой степени. Согласно данным объективного исследования следует, что за не большим исключением, общие нарушения в двух группах были схожими, преобладала легкая микросимптоматика с преобладанием координаторных нарушений у детей старшей группы. Вегетативные нарушения проявлялись полиморфизмом клинических проявлений в виде как симпатикотонии, так и парасимпатикотонии.

Ключевые слова: черепно-мозговая травма, вегетативная нервная система, невротический статус, посттравматическая энцефалопатия

Введение. Черепно-мозговая травма (ЧМТ) является одной из серьезнейших проблем современной медицины, актуальность которой не вызывает сомнений. В общей структуре ЧМТ детский травматизм составляет 21–75%. Соотношение мальчики/девочки среди пациентов с ЧМТ варьирует от 2:1 до 3:1. ЧМТ у детей занимает первое место среди всех травм, а ее распространенность составляет от 1,2 до 11,2%. Выраженность психоневрологических нарушений в отдаленном периоде ЧМТ во многом определяется степенью её тяжести. Хотя в структуре закрытой ЧМТ 76–89% случаев приходится на лёгкие формы (А.Н. Коновалов, Л.Б. Лихтерман, А.А. Потапов, 1998; А.С. Петрухин, 2004), именно последствия тяжёлой и среднетяжёлой ЧМТ оказывают значительное негативное влияние на дальнейшее развитие детей. Важно, что последствия ЗЧМТ могут проявиться не сразу, а оказаться отсроченными. Таким образом, резюмируя данные литературы по распространенности и структуре детского нейротравматизма можно сделать вывод, что ЧМТ является достаточно часто встречающейся патологией детского возраста.

Цель исследования. Изучить клинико-неврологические особенности у детей с посттравматической энцефалопатии в зависимости от степени тяжести (сотрясение или ушиб).

Материалы и методы исследования. В исследование было включено 100 детей с диагнозом последствия перенесенной ЧМТ лёгкой и средне – тяжёлой степени. Все пациенты нами были разделены на две группы. В 1-ю группу были включены 50 пациента с диагнозом последствия перенесенной ЧМТ легкой степени, а 2-я группа включала в себя 50 пациента с диагнозом последствия перенесенной ЧМТ среднетяжелой степени. В первой группе обследованных количество мальчиков было выше, чем девочек – 33 (66%) и 17 (34%) соответственно, а во второй группе данное различие было незначительно меньше – 29 (58%) и 21 (42%) соответственно. Что касается возрастных показателей, в группе с ЧМТ легкой степени группа детей в возрасте от 7 до 11 лет составляла 48%, а 12-18 лет-52%, тогда как в группе с ЧМТ средне – тяжёлой степени в значительной степени преобладала старшая группа от 12 до 18 лет – 66%, тогда как младшая группа 7-11 лет составляла 34%).

У всех исследуемых осуществлялось стандартное объективное клинико-неврологическое обследование по стандартной схеме с учетом общего состояния ребенка, соматического статуса, состояния черепно-мозговых нервов (ЧМН), двигательной и чувствительной сферы, координаторной функции, наличия менингеальных симптомов. Для диагностики наличия синдрома вегетативной дистонии (СВД) использовались: «Вопросник для выявления признаков вегетативных нарушений», состоящий из 11-ти пунктов, заполняемый больным (если общее количество баллов равно или более 15-ти, предполагали наличие СВД)

Результаты. По результатам неврологического осмотра было видно, что у детей 7 – 11 лет I группы, относительно преобладала микросимптоматика в виде болезненности т. Валле – 75% (12-18 лет – 73,1%), легкого снижения мышечного тонуса – 54,2% (12-18 лет – 38,5%), симптома Данцинг-Кункова –

75,% (12-18 лет – 73,1%) и достоверно выше отмечались легкие гиперкинезы языка – 54,2%, тогда как у старших детей I группы достоверно выше проявлялись симптомы расстройства координаторной сферы, это нистагм – 34,6%, адиадохокинез – 42,3%, неустойчивость в позе Ромберга – 50%, интенционный тремор – 80,8%, помимо вышеперечисленного с достоверным преобладанием у старших детей отмечались онемения и гипестезия. Достоверные и относительные показатели II группы пациентов с последствиями ЧМТ среднетяжелой степени, практически не отличались от I группы. Также следует отметить высокие показатели “оживления” сухожильных рефлексов в обеих группах.

Для определения функционального состояния ВНС нами проводились исследования при помощи таблицы Гийома-Вейна, которая давала возможность определить признаки вегетативных изменений, что выявляло наличие соматоформного расстройства ВНС. По этим результатам было видно, что симпатическая направленность ВНС отмечалась достоверно выше в группе пациентов с последствиями средне – тяжелой степени – 72,1%, парасимпатическая направленность достоверно выше наблюдалась у больных с последствиями легкой степени – 45,9%. Сравнительный анализ вегетативной нервной системы по вопроснику в группах двух нозологий дал относительно одинаковые результаты, которые достоверно выше были у детей в возрасте 12–18 лет обеих групп. Отличия зависели и от пола детей. Достоверное превалирование соматоформного расстройства ВНС зафиксировано у девочек по сравнению с мальчиками ($p < 0,05$). В структуре соматоформных расстройств ВНС в I и во II группе доминировали раздражительность – I гр. – 83,6%, II гр. – 85,3%, покраснение лица – 76,4% и 72,1% соответственно, быстрая утомляемость с достоверным преобладанием во II группе чем в I гр. – 32,9% и 48,2%, тревожные состояния, которые также были достоверно выше во второй группе – 42,6%. Среди детей с последствиями ЧМТ, признаки вегетативной дисрегуляции в виде астенических симптомов, кардиоваскулярных и респираторных расстройств встречались с наибольшей

частотой, данные симптомы достоверно чаще регистрировалось в группе подростков с последствиями ЧМТ среднетяжёлой степени. Отмечались также диссомнические и гастроинтестинальные нарушения.

Выводы. Итак, по данным невростатуса следует, имело место отсутствие грубой очаговой симптоматики, лёгкая микросимптоматика преобладала в основном у детей младшего возраста в обеих группах не зависимо от пола, координаторные нарушения достоверно доминировали у детей старшего возраста, что соответствует литературным данным. В сравниваемых группах преобладали вегетативных расстройств как в сторону симпатикотонии, так и в сторону парасимпатикотонии, это проявления разных форм дезадаптации. А также, по полученным результатам можно говорить о существующей взаимосвязи последствий ЧМТ легкой и среднетяжёлой степени с синдромом вегетативной дистонии.

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Синдром головной боли при Ковиде -19

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Аннотация: По статистике головная боль при коронавирусе встречается у $\frac{1}{3}$ заболевших. Но такие ощущения могут сопровождать и другие интоксикационные состояния. Цефалгия – медицинское название симптома, встречается также при патологиях нервной и сердечно-сосудистой систем. Поэтому важно знать особенности и характер головных болей при Ковид-19, чтобы не спутать их с признаками других заболеваний. Данная публикация раскрывает отличительные черты при цефалгии при КОВИД - 19

Ключевые слова: Цефалгия, COVID-19, неврологические осложнения, умеренные когнитивные расстройства.

Введение: Цефалгия при коронавирусной инфекции служит наиболее частым общемозговым симптомом, и ее этиология переменчива. Можно выделить следующие варианты цефалгий в условиях пандемии COVID-19:

- 1) цефалгии, обусловленные ношением средств противовирусной защиты, как за счет физического дискомфорта, так и на фоне гипоксии при длительном ношении масок и респираторов;
- 2) цефалгии, обусловленные приемом медикаментозных препаратов, и ятрогенные цефалгии;
- 3) цефалгии на фоне астенодепрессивного состояния в условиях вынужденных ограничений и самоизоляции, а также обусловленные тревожно-фобическими расстройствами;
- 4) цефалгии, обусловленные непосредственным воздействием вируса SARS-CoV-2.

В тезисе приводятся результаты исследования больных с COVID-19 с цереброваскулярной патологией. Наиболее распространенным клиническим симптомом заболевания является нарушение когнитивных функций и головные боли. Уже на самых ранних стадиях ХИМ у 85-90% пациентов выявляются когнитивные нарушения различной степени выраженности, которые при заболевании COVID-19 прогрессируют.

Целью исследования явилось изучение когнитивных функций на основании клинико-неврологического обследования больных с ХИМ 1-2 стадии, перенесших COVID-19.

Материалы и методы исследования: Исходя из клинических особенностей коронавирусной инфекции, а также ссылаясь на Международную классификацию МКБ-10 (U09.9), все пациенты были выделены по группам. Первую группу составили 50 обследованных с диагнозом последствия перенесённой коронавирусной инфекции лёгкой степени, вторую группу – 50 обследованных с диагнозом последствия перенесённой коронавирусной инфекции среднетяжёлой степени. Изучение структуры коронавирусной инфекции в зависимости от пола и возраста показало, что в возрасте 35-45 лет в обеих группах частота встречаемости как легкой, так и средне-тяжёлой степени последствий коронавируса, у мужчин была больше чем у женщин 13 (59,09%), 11 (55,00%) 9 (40,91%), 9 (45,00%) соответственно. Такое же соотношение было и в обеих группах больных 55-60 лет, мужчины I группа 15 (53,57%), женщины 13 (46,43%), II группа мужчины 19 (63,33%), женщины 11 (36,67%). Особенностью постковидной ГБ показали, что при последствиях коронавирусной инфекции может отмечаться характер различных типов цефалгии. Однако у большинства больных обеих групп, перенёвших коронавирус – 48,00% и 64,00% соответственно, в структуре цефалгического синдрома преобладали ГБ, соответствующие головным болям напряжения.

Выводы: По полученным результатам клинико-неврологического обследования можно определенно сказать, что при последствиях COVID-19 легкой и среднетяжёлой степени отсутствовали грубые очаговые неврологические нарушения

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Клинические и биохимические особенности прогрессирующих мышечных дистрофий

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Аннотация. Нейромышечные заболевания (НМЗ) — гетерогенная группа заболеваний, в основе которых лежит генетически детерминированное поражение определенной анатомической структуры нейромышечного аппарата. Актуальность проблемы НМЗ определяется высокой суммарной распространенностью данной группы заболеваний в популяции и тяжелой инвалидизацией больных. Согласно международной базе данных генетической информации известно более 7500 наследственных синдромов, из них более 500 протекают с поражением нервной системы, включая около 200 нозологических форм нейромышечной патологии.

Ключевые слова: нервно-мышечные заболевания, миопатия, прогрессирующие мышечные дистрофии.

Annotation. Neuromuscular diseases (NMD) are a heterogeneous group of diseases, which are based on a genetically determined lesion of a certain anatomical structure of the neuromuscular apparatus. The relevance of the NMD problem is determined by the high total prevalence of this group of diseases in the population and severe disability of patients. According to the international database of genetic information, more than 7,500 hereditary syndromes are known, of which more than 500 occur with damage to the nervous system, including about 200 nosological forms of neuromuscular pathology.

Key words: neuromuscular diseases, myopathy, progressive muscular dystrophies.

Общая распространенность прогрессирующих мышечных дистрофий (ПМД) составляет 200 случаев на 1 000 000 населения, что позволяет отнести их к наиболее частым формам наследственной патологии. Наиболее часто в структуре ПМД встречается ПМД Дюшенна — 9,6 на 100 000 мужского населения, ПМД Беккера — 5,0 на 100 000. Частота встречаемости других

форм ПМД в популяции ниже. Распространенность ПМД Ландузи - Дежерина - 2,9 на 100 000 человек.

Данные мировой литературы позволили подчеркнуть, что нервно-мышечная патология является самой распространенной группой среди всех наследственных болезней нервной системы. В связи с этим большое практическое значение имеет проблема ранней диагностики, в первую очередь лечатся многие формы, результат которых определяется временем начала лечения. Запоздалая диагностика связана с упущенными терапевтическими возможностями.

Клинико-синдромный метод диагностики нервно-мышечных заболеваний основан на сборе анамнеза и оценке клинического состояния. Различные типы НМЗ имеют схожие клинические проявления, независимо от вовлеченного гена. Заболевание чаще начинается в детском возрасте - 5-12 лет. Синдром мышечной слабости при нервно-мышечных заболеваниях составляет основу комплекса клинических симптомов и представлен следующими критериями рефлекторных нарушений: - симметричная мышечная слабость и гипотрофия конечностей, клинически характеризующаяся нарушением функции ходьбы (утиная походка); трудности при беге, прыжках.

Но вышеперечисленные клинические проявления необратимы и развиваются со временем. Актуальны раннее доклиническое выявление характерных биохимических изменений при ПМД и ранняя их коррекция. В связи с этим мы поставили перед собой следующую цель.

Цель исследования: изучить клинические, нейрофизиологические и биохимические особенности ПМД и разработать вопросы оптимизации их диагностики и лечения.

Методы исследования:

1. Клинико-неврологическое обследование.
2. Электронейромиография.
3. Анализ КФК, ЛДГ в крови.

Выводы. Ранние клинические признаки, повышение активности АСТ, АЛТ и креатинфосфокиназы в крови являются основанием для назначения молекулярно-генетического исследования. Данная схема может быть использована для сокращения длительности поиска неврологической и инфекционной патологии, отсутствующей в диагнозе ПМД, назначения своевременного и адекватного лечения, улучшения качества жизни больного ребенка. Хотя заболевание неизлечимо, при нем показано проведение терапии. Целью лечения является поддержание мышечной функции, а также предотвращение контрактур.

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Шейные дорсалгии и их клинико-неврологическое течение

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Аннотация:

Боль в спине или шее (дорсалгия) переживают в течение жизни подавляющее большинство населения планеты, дорсалгия находится на втором месте по распространенности, уступая лишь простудным заболеваниям. Данная публикация рассматривает шейные дорсалгии и их клинико-неврологическое течение

Ключевые слова: Дорсалгия, боль, шейный отдел, невростатус

Актуальность проблемы: Шейный отдел позвоночника - самый подвижных отдел позвоночника. Наиболее частые причины боли: миофасциальный синдром- спазм подзатылочных мышц (мышц Вернье), поверхностных и глубоких разгибателей головы и шеи; вертеброгенные причины: нестабильность позвонков, артроз дугоотростчатых суставов (фасеточный синдром)

Боль в спине или шее (дорсалгия) переживают в течение жизни подавляющее большинство населения планеты, дорсалгия находится на втором месте по распространенности, уступая лишь простудным заболеваниям.

Цель исследования: определить клинико-неврологические особенности шейных дорсалгий у взрослых пациентов.

Материал и методы. Нами обследованы 214 человек с шейными дорсалгиями (ШД) – 86 (40,2%) мужчин (22-60 лет средний возраст – $37,9 \pm 5,4$ лет) и 128 (59,8%) женщин в возрасте от 21 до 55 лет (в среднем $41,1 \pm 6,1$ лет).

Все пациенты были зрелого возраста, на который приходится пик личной, социальной и профессиональной работоспособности. Нами проведен комплексный клинико-неврологический осмотр, применены исследовательские шкалы: визуально-аналоговая шкала боли (ВАШ), индекс мышечного синдрома (ИМС). Применяли и радиологические методы исследования – КТ и МРТ.

Результаты исследования. При обращении боль в покое по ВАШ среднем составляла $4,3 \pm 0,3$ балла, т.е. была умеренной интенсивности, а после физической нагрузки у 164 (76,64%) пациентов интенсивность возрастала до $6,2 \pm 0,4$ баллов – становилась выраженной, постепенно снижаясь в покое. Боль была умеренной у 111 (57,87%) больных, выраженной – у 87 (40,65%) пациентов, резко выраженной – у 11 (5,14%) пациентов. Слабейшая средняя боль составляла $3,0 \pm 0,4$ балла, а сильнейшая – $7,8 \pm 0,7$ балла.

Напряжение мышц шеи ограничивало движения в шейном отделе позвоночника, что приводило у всех больных к наклону линии плеч, у четверти – к асимметрии плеч, у 43 (20,09%) больных I группы – к кифозу шейного отдела, а у 51 (23,83%) больных этой группы – к функциональному кифозу шейного отдела без структурных изменений на КТ и/или МРТ.

Констатация наличия или отсутствия активного воспалительного компонента ШД позволяло нам принимать решение о тактике терапии и ее компонентности. Уровень активного воспаления пациентов позволил нам выделить часть пациентов с явным признаком воспалительного генеза обострения ШД – 52 (24,3%) пациента (СОЭ – $26,2 \pm 3,8$ мм/ч, лейкоциты – $10,3 \pm 1,7 \cdot 10^9$ /л, СРБ – $11,4 \pm 2,6$ мг/л). У остальных 162 (75,7%) уровни маркеров воспаления колебались в пределах допустимых норм. Соотношения воспалительных и не воспалительных ШД составили 1:3,12, то есть более $\frac{3}{4}$ пациентов с ШД имеют не воспалительный генез обострений.

Рентгеноморфологические признаки компенсаторной гипермобильности позвонков существенно зависят от продолжительности болезни. Рефлекторная миофиксация в позвоночно-дисковом сегменте (ПДС) отмечена у всех (100%) наблюдавшихся больных с нейропатическими болями с длительностью заболевания от 3 лет. А у всех пациентов с ноцицептивными болями после 7 лет развивается внутридисковая дистрофия. На КТ и МРТ у 47 (21,96%) больных констатировали уменьшение высоты межпозвонковых поясничных дисков I-II стадий и у 21 (9,81%) больных спондилоартроз III стадии.

Заключение. При обследовании пациентов с ШД нами выявлены дистрофически-дегенеративные процессы и другие патологии шейного отдела позвоночника у 36,92% пациентов с болью в области шеи, у остальных 63,08% боли не имели отношение к патологии позвоночника и являлись миофасциальными, воспалительный генез болей отметили у 26,17% пациентов и функциональные миофасциальные боли – у 73,83%. Соотношения воспалительных и не воспалительных ШД составили 1:3,12, то есть более $\frac{3}{4}$ пациентов с ШД имеют не воспалительный генез обострений и не нуждаются в назначении курса НПВС.

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The Scientific Basis for the Study of Syntax and Punctuation.

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One of the most important tasks of the lessons of the native language in the primary grades is to develop in children the ability to consciously use the sentence to express their thoughts. The importance of working on a proposal is primarily due to its social function. To teach students to consciously use a sentence means to develop their ability to divide the flow of speech into complete structural and semantic units, to isolate the subject of thought, to formulate a thought structurally and intonation, combining words into sentences. It should also be noted that the assimilation of morphology, vocabulary, phonetics, spelling is carried out on a syntactic basis.

The program in the native language involves the development of students' speech, improving their speech culture. Conscious knowledge about the sentence and its constituent parts, about words and phrases helps children in the correct formation of sentences, in their grammatically accurate use.

Syntax is the rules for connecting words: these are the laws of expressing objective and subjective information with the help of a word, this is the basis of our speech behavior and our mutual understanding. The basic unit of syntax is the sentence. The accuracy of the transmission and the adequacy of the perception of information depend on how the sentence is constructed. The minimal unit of syntax is the syntactic form of a word (or syntax me). Syntactic forms form phrases and sentences. Sentences are combined into complex sentences, and also form the maximum syntactic unit - the text. The text and the sentence are called the communicative level of syntax. The term "syntax" refers not only to a certain side of the language, but also to the branch of linguistics that studies this side. Methodology for working with phrases.

The concept of "phrase" shows that we are talking about a combination of two or more words that are related in meaning and grammatically. The connection

between words is established with the help of a question. In a phrase, one of the words is the main one (the question is raised from it), and the other is dependent.

Working on a phrase in elementary school solves the following problems:

- development of thinking and speech;
- formation of spelling skills;
- awareness of phrases as a special unit of language that serves to form sentences.

The forms and methods of working on the phrase are:

1. Compilation of phrases from these words.
2. Asking questions from word to word.
3. Compilation of phrases and definition of gender, number, case.
4. Declension of phrases consisting of an adjective and a noun.
5. Compilation of verb phrases and recognition of cases of nouns.
6. Composing phrases using verbs and prepositions.
7. Replacing phrases that are opposite in meaning.
8. Selection of phrases that are close in meaning.

To form the spelling skill of case endings of nouns, the following types of exercises are recommended in composing phrases:

1. Put the nouns in the right case, highlight the case endings of the nouns.
2. Write out phrases from the sentence.
3. Choose dependent words for this word.
4. Compose phrases using these words, determine the case of nouns.

Work on the phrase contributes to the development of speech and thinking, enrichment of the vocabulary of students, the formation of spelling skills, improving the culture of speech. The formation of students' ability to establish the connection of words in a sentence is one of the most important syntactic and speech skills. The ability to isolate a phrase in a sentence is formed gradually and requires a long training. The following types of exercises are especially effective:

1. Work on the intonation of the sentence.
2. Isolation of sentences from the flow of speech.
3. Distribution of the offer.

4. Restoration of the deformed proposal.
5. Editing offers.
6. Analysis of the proposal and drawing up its scheme.
7. Drawing up a proposal according to this scheme.
8. Drawing up a story with subsequent analysis of sentences of a certain structure.

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The role of changes in DNA methylation in the development of burnout syndrome.

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Abstract. The publication discusses changes in DNA that may be the cause of the development of burnout syndrome.

Keywords: burnout, DNA, methylation.

The syndrome or phenomenon of "burnout" occurs in situations of intense professional communication under the influence of many external and internal factors. It was first described by HJ Freudenberger in 1974 as a response to uncomfortable working conditions, in the form of "a state of emotional, physical and mental fatigue as a result of working conditions.

Research points to epigenetic and functional changes in at least two types of genes: those that directly control the function of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system, and those that cause long-term dysregulation of neuronal processes, and are important for the proper regulation of mood, emotion, and cognition. Klengel T. et al (2014), Januar V. et al (2015) found that DNA methylation plays an important role in the pathogenesis of various stress-related mental disorders such as major depressive disorder and post-traumatic stress disorder.

Marchand A. et al (2014) suggest differentiating burnout and depression using various parameters related to cortisol activity. It is assumed that hypercortisolism is associated with distress and depression, while burnout is more often accompanied by hypocortisolism and may be accompanied by various changes in the DNA methylation patterns of the GR gene.

Increased expression of GR enhances negative feedback, leading to hyporeactivity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system and, as a consequence, hypocortisolism.

SLC6A4, a gene associated with the production of serotonin, can be considered as a biomarker gene for burnout. It is the only gene currently associated with burnout, which shows hypermethylation of SLC6A4.

SEB or prolonged occupational stress correlated with certain anatomical and functional characteristics of the brain. For example, Jovanovic et al. (2011) showed that subjects with chronic work stress had a functional lack of connectivity between the amygdala and the medial prefrontal cortex, including the anterior cingulate cortex.

Moreover, it was found that the number of receptors that are involved in the regulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system (5-HT_{1A} receptors) was reduced in the anterior cingulate gyrus, insular cortex and in the hippocampus. Similarly, Blix E. et al (2013) observed a decrease in the gray matter volumes of the anterior cingulate gyrus and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, as well as a decrease in the volumes of the caudate nucleus and putamen. Savic I. (2015) observed that patients with burnout had a significantly thinner mesial frontal cortex and selective changes in subcortical formations: the size of the amygdala was increased on both sides, and the volume of the caudate nucleus decreased.

Clear aligners.

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Abstract. The publication deals with the issue of the manufacture and use of clear aligners in dentistry.

Keywords: clear aligners, orthodontics, dentoalveolar anomalies.

There is the significant increase in Uzbekistan in the number of orthodontic patients who seek clear aligners treatment for reasons of aesthetics and convenience.

Indications for the use of clear aligners include: diastema and trema up to 6 mm; crowding of teeth; tort anomalies of teeth; crossbite; deep bite; distal bite; open bite; creating a place for the future implant.

There are also contraindications: allergic reaction to thermoform plastic; tooth mobility III and IV degrees; severe forms of inflammatory-destructive periodontal diseases.

Clear aligners are produced from polymer plates of various thicknesses, which, when heated, become plastic and allow duplication of real or simulated objects of various shapes by pressing in the apparatus.

Clear aligners manufacturing process

1. Formation of initial data: the orthodontist takes impressions from the patient's dental rows (or scans them) and sends them to the laboratory along with OPTG (or cone-beam computed tomography of the teeth), as well as photographs of the patient - face without a smile, face with a smile, profile without a smile, profile with a smile.
2. 3D scanning of models: based on the received material, a digital model of teeth is obtained using a 3D scanner to develop a subsequent treatment plan. The scanning accuracy is 10 microns.
3. Treatment planning: based on the received digital model of teeth in the modeling program (most often Maestro 3D Dental Studio), a treatment plan is developed. The path of tooth movement is calculated and the required number of clear aligners is determined. The program segments the movements of the teeth into stages according to a given algorithm.

4. Model 3D printing: Step-by-step (according to the dynamics of future treatment) accurate models of the patient's teeth are made using digital 3D printing.

5. Thermoforming: Mouthguards are made from special plastic by thermoforming. It is thin, durable, transparent; it has a shape memory due to the silicone built into its structure, strength due to the properties of plastic.

6. Processing and polishing and sterilization of aligners. Clear aligners are placed in individual sterile bags and are scheduled according to the terms of their wearing.

Compared to conventional fixed orthodontic appliances, there is evidence that clear aligners cause less harm to oral hygiene.

These devices are removable and the daily hygiene procedures of patients are not difficult. The safety of aligners for oral mucosal epithelium has also been confirmed in vitro.

There have been concerns that aligner treatment could lead to poor oral hygiene, as nearly 24-hour coverage of all tooth surfaces and marginal gingiva interferes with self-cleaning by saliva, increases soft plaque buildup, and can irritate periodontal tissues, which in turn can lead to chronic inflammation.

However, these effects were not observed in the study by Zhao R. et al. (2020), which may be due to the good awareness of patients about oral hygiene and the fact that the edges of the aligners are modeled below the marginal gingiva.

Moreover, the surface of the clear aligners is smooth, and each pair of aligners is used for no more than 14 days, so the formation of biofilm is much less than with traditional fixed orthodontic and removable appliances. Clear aligners fit snugly to the teeth and can act as a barrier to food debris washed out by saliva to bacteria in the mouth. In addition, since the leveling elements cover a large part of the tooth crown, the force and direction of movement is more easily dosed and controlled, the teeth move more evenly in relation to each other, which prevents supragingival plaque from migrating into the subgingival region, preventing infection and destruction of periodontal tissues.

Сравнительная характеристика терапии меноррагии при аденомиозе

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Резюме. С целью оценки эффективности терапии менометроррагией у пациентов с аденомиозом, пациентки были распределены в 2 группы. I А группа (20 женщин в возрасте 28-33) проведена терапия препаратом Савис: диеногест 2 мг (производитель Гедеон Рихтер, Венгрия); I Б группе (20 женщин) в возрасте 34-39) больных проведена терапия установлением внутриматочной спирали Мирена. Второй группе пациенток (20 женщин в возрасте 40-45 лет) проведена комбинированная терапия: гистероскопическая абляция с применением в последующем ВМС «Мирена». Полученные результаты проведенного исследования показали высокую эффективность комбинированной терапии с использованием гистероскопической абляции с введением левоноргестрелсодержащей ВМС при меноррагии у женщин с аденомиозом.

Ключевые слова: аденомиоз, менометроррагия, диеногест, левоноргестрелсодержащая ВМС, вагинальное кровомазание.

В структуре гинекологической заболеваемости аденомиоз занимает одно из ведущих мест и встречается у 12–50 % женщин репродуктивного возраста. [3] По данным литературных источников аденомиоз является частой причиной менометроррагии, дисменореи, бесплодия, хронических тазовых болей различной интенсивности, нередко приводящих к психосоматическим и вегетативным нарушениям (2, 4, 1, 5, 7). Оценка качества жизни у пациенток с аденомиозом исследователями показала его влияние на многие аспекты жизни женщины, в том числе на работу, получение образования, социальные взаимоотношения [6].

В настоящее время однозначный подход к лечению эндометриоза отсутствует [8]. В связи с этим поиск терапии, обеспечивающая нормализацию менструального цикла, предупреждения рецидива менометроррагии и улучшения качества жизни женщины является актуальной.

Цель исследования: оценить эффективность терапии у пациентов с аденомиозом, протекающий менометроррагией

Материалы и методы исследования.

Нами обследовано 70 женщин с менометроррагией, у пациенток с аденомиозом матки, которые были распределены на 2 группы рандомизированно - методом случайной выборки. Больные первой основной группы в свою очередь будет разделена на 2 подгруппы: I А группа (20 женщин в возрасте 28-33) проведена терапия препаратом Савис: диеногест 2 мг (производитель Гедеон Рихтер, Венгрия); I Б группе (20 женщин) в возрасте 34-39) больных проведена терапия установлением левоноргестрелсодержащей внутриматочной спирали (ВМС) Мирена. Второй группе пациенток (20 женщин в возрасте 40-45 лет) проведена гистероскопическая абляция с применением в последующем ВМС «Мирена». Для контрольной группы было отобрано 10 женщин без аденомиоза с нормальным регулярным менструальным циклом.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ И ИХ ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ

Анализ проведенных нами исследования показал, что оральная гормональная терапия эффективнее при меноррагиях в первой стадии аденомиоза. Так, в период наблюдения женщин I А группы терапии препаратом Савис, гиперполименорея не наблюдалась у женщин с аденомиозом первой стадии (из 6 женщин). Между тем, у женщин второй стадии аденомиоза (из 9 женщин) гиперполименорея наблюдалась у 3 (33,3%) и у 3 женщин - третьей стадии (60,0%). После 6 месяца курса лечения, пациенты II и III стадии аденомиоза было пролонгирована терапия препаратом Савис, однако достоверных изменений симптома гиперполименорей не наблюдались по сравнению предыдущим курсом лечения данным препаратом, однако болевой синдром прекратился.

У женщин группы I Б (ВМС-Мирена), гиперполименорея не наблюдалось, у пациенток I (4 женщин) и II стадии, (8 женщин(за исключением 4 женщин пациенток второй стадии, где в течении первых 3 месяцев наблюдалось

вагинальное межменструальное кровомазание. У пациенток III стадии аденомиоза (8 женщин) у 3-х (37,5%) продолжала гиперполименорея, на фоне которой у одной была экспульсия ВМС, а у остальных 5 пациенток наблюдалось вагинальное межменструальное кровомазание в течение 6 месяцев у 4 пациенток и в течение 9 месяцев у остальных 2-х женщин III стадии.

Эффективность лечения симптома гиперполименореи независимо от стадии аденомиоза была достоверно выше у пациенток II группы, чем I А и I Б группе. Так, у 17 пациенток (85,0%) была аменорея, у 3-х женщин (15,0%) гипоменорея.

Таким образом, полученные результаты проведенного исследования показали высокую эффективность комбинированной терапии с использованием гистероскопической абляции с введением левоноргестрелсодержащей ВМС при меноррагии у женщин с аденомиозом.

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Особенности клинического течения вич инфекции на фоне туберкулёза у детей

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Progression of hiv-infection combined with tuberculosis in children

Resume. The article presents the results of observation of 57 patients with HIV infection combined with tuberculosis in children. The comparison group consisted of 23 children of HIV-infected children without tuberculosis, of the same age. Laboratory methods for studying the immune status, the level of CD4 cells; Bacterioscopy and sputum culture. Immunodiagnostics: (Mantoux test with 2TE and recombinant tuberculosis allergen - DIASKINTEST). X-ray examination.

The results of the study showed that against the background of secondary immunodeficiency caused by HIV, TB acquires a generalized character with multiple lesions of internal organs and the central nervous system, more rapid progression of the disease.

Keywords: HIV infection, tuberculosis, children, disease progression

Актуальность. В глобальном масштабе туберкулез (ТБ) — одна из главных причин смертности у ВИЧ-инфицированных лиц. В настоящее время проблема туберкулеза в сочетании с ВИЧ-инфекцией является одной из самых актуальных. Туберкулез у больных ВИЧ-инфекцией среди вторичных заболеваний занимает первое место и составляет 30-50% случаев, а смертность от него достигает 43-89% [1,3,6]. Заболеваемость туберкулезом и смертность от туберкулеза больных ВИЧ-инфекцией в 29 и 31 раз соответственно превышает заболеваемость и смертность постоянного населения без ВИЧ-инфекции [2,4]. Пандемия СПИДа — уникальное явление в истории человечества из-за скорости распространения, масштабов и глубины последствий. Впервые новая инфекция (в своей заключительной стадии) была официально зарегистрирована Центром по контролю над заболеваниями США (CDC) в 1981 г. когда стали поступать сообщения о молодых гомосексуалистах, заболевших пневмоцистной пневмонией или саркомой

Капоши. В обеих группах при обследовании выявлялось выраженное угнетение системы иммунитета. Среди больных ВИЧ-инфекцией растет число лиц, у которых развиваются поздние стадии болезни. Это приводит к росту заболеваемости туберкулезом среди больных с выраженным иммунодефицитом. Значительное внимание ученых всего мира обращено оппортунистическим заболеваниям. Среди которых у больных ВИЧ-инфекцией лидирующее место занимает туберкулез (ТБ), являющийся частой причиной их смерти [5]. Динамика распространения сочетанной патологии ВИЧ/ТБ в РФ в первом десятилетии XXI века представляет собой восходящий тренд, который при сохранении темпов роста, в ближайшие 5 лет приведет к лавинообразному росту числа больных сочетанной патологией.

Цель исследования - изучить клинические проявления ВИЧ-инфекции в сочетании с туберкулёзом у детей

Материалы и методы. Проведено клинический: обследование 57 больных ВИЧ-инфекции в сочетании с туберкулёзом у детей, от 4-х лет до 15 лет, Контрольную группу (n=23) составили ВИЧ инфицированные дети, без туберкулеза. Лабораторные методы включали в себе изучение общего анализа крови, кала, мочи, уровня CD4 клеток. Проводили всем больным с ТБ бактериоскопию и посев мокроты. Всем детям проведено иммунодиагностика ТБ: (Пробу Манту с 2ТЕ и аллергеном туберкулезным рекомбинантным - ДИАСКИНТЕСТ). Так же проводили рентгенологическое исследование органов грудной клетки.

Результаты и обсуждение. Для выполнения поставленных задач нами проводилось клиническое обследование 57 детей для изучения особенностей ВИЧ - инфицированных детей сочетанной с туберкулёзом, в возрасте от 4 лет до 15 лет. Мальчиков было 32(56,14%) и девочек- 25(43,86%). По возрасту дети распределились следующим образом: от 4 лет до 6 лет – 34(59,65%) детей, от 6 лет до 10 лет – 13(22,81%) и от 10 до 15 лет – 10(17,55%) детей. Группу сравнения составили 23 детей ВИЧ - инфицированных детей без туберкулёза, того же возраста. Результаты повторных обследований на ВИЧ были у них

отрицательными. В зависимости от степени выраженности туберкулезного процесса, которая оценивалась по традиционным параметрам у пациентов первой группы (ВИЧ/ТБ) были инфильтративный туберкулез легких был – у 15 (26,32%) больных, инфильтративный туберкулез легких в фазе распада – у 10 (17,55%), фиброзно-кавернозный туберкулез легких – у 9 (15,79 %), диссеминированный туберкулез легких (ДТ) - у 11 (19,3%), генерализованный туберкулез (ГТ) – у 6 (10,53%), туберкулезный плеврит (ТП) - у 6 (10,53%) больных. Микобактерии туберкулеза обнаружены у 39 (68,43%) пациентов. У больных второй группы (ВИЧ) в группе больных, где была диагностирована только ВИЧ-инфекция без активного туберкулеза III стадия ВИЧ-инфекции была диагностирована у 14 больных (60,87%), IVA стадия - у 4 больных (17,39%), IVБ стадия у 2 (8,69%) и IVВ стадия - у 2 пациентов (8,69%). Поскольку у большинства больных с сочетанной патологией (ВИЧ/ТБ) диагноз туберкулеза определял стадию ВИЧ-инфекции, доля больных с «поздними» стадиями ВИЧ-инфекции (стадии IVБ и IVВ) была существенно большей, чем у больных ВИЧ-инфекцией без туберкулеза (43,86% и 21,74% соответственно). Классическим признаком прогрессирования ВИЧ-инфекции является снижение числа CD4-лимфоцитов. Количественная характеристика последних является одним из важных показателей диагностики степени развития иммунодефицита, а также одним из ведущих критериев установления стадии ВИЧ-инфекции. При оценке количественных показателей уровня CD4+Т-лимфоцитов было обнаружено прогрессивное снижение их числа с $0,568 \pm 0,033 \times 10^9/\text{л}$ в III стадию до $0,129 \pm 0,028 \times 10^9/\text{л}$ в IVВ стадию при сочетанной инфекции (при ВИЧ-инфекции без туберкулеза с $0,634 \pm 0,030 \times 10^9/\text{л}$ до $0,098 \pm 0,064 \times 10^9/\text{л}$) при показателях в контрольной группе $0,760 \pm 0,040 \times 10^9/\text{л}$. Уровень CD8+ Т-лимфоцитов в III стадию в обеих группах оказался даже увеличенным по сравнению с контрольными данными и, поэтому, дальнейшее снижение числа клеток данной субпопуляции к IVВ стадии хотя и было отмечено, но не носило столь драматического характера, как в случае с CD4+ клетками. Противоположно направленные сдвиги

количественных показателей CD4+ и CD8+Т-лимфоцитов в обеих группах инфицированных больных способствовали выраженному снижению иммунорегуляторного коэффициента уже в III стадии ВИЧ-инфекции ($0,57 \pm 0,05$ при сочетанной инфекции и $0,75 \pm 0,06$ при ВИЧ-инфекции без туберкулеза), без достоверных различий в динамике ВИЧ-инфекции в обеих группах пациентов ($p > 0,01$; $p > 0,05$). Как и предполагалось, минимальные уровни соотношения Тх/Тс формировались в IVB стадию ВИЧ-инфекции ($0,20 \pm 0,06$ при сочетанной инфекции и $0,17 \pm 0,03$ при моноинфекции), являясь еще одним показателем тяжести иммунодефицита.

Заключение. Таким образом, течение сочетанной инфекции ВИЧ/ТБ отличается от ВИЧ-инфекции без туберкулеза целым комплексом добавочных воздействий, утяжеляющих общее состояние больных. сопутствующие заболевания с формированием осложнений, признаками инфекционно-токсического, астеновегетативного синдромов, с прогрессированием иммунодефицита ухудшали течение заболевания инфицированных детей, и приводили к тяжелому течению ВИЧ - инфекции, сочетанной с туберкулёзом у детей. На фоне вторичного иммунодефицита, обусловленного ВИЧ, ТБ приобретает генерализированный характер с множественными поражениями внутренних органов и ЦНС, более быстрому прогрессированию заболевания.

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Клинико - биохимические проявления поражения печени у больных туберкулезом легких с разным генетическим фоном

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Annotation

In order to study the frequency and nature of liver damage, 337 tuberculosis patients with different genetic backgrounds were examined. The genetic background of the organism and the activity of liver indicator enzymes were determined.

The presence of liver pathology was found in 94 (27.8±2.4%) patients. It is proved that the most frequent and severe manifestations of liver damage were detected in patients with an unfavorable genetic background. Clinical manifestations from the liver correlated with changes in biochemical parameters.

Key words: tuberculosis, liver damage, genetic background

Актуальность. При туберкулезе легких (ТЛ) печень закономерно вовлекается в патологический процесс. Туберкулезная интоксикация создает предпосылки для поражения печени, угнетая ферментативную активность, вызывая различные морфологические изменения [5,4].

Патология печени у больных туберкулезом отличается большим разнообразием этиологических и патогенетических факторов. Следует отметить, что у больных туберкулезом легких чаще имеет место наличие 2-х и более факторов, вызывающих комбинированное поражение печени, что затрудняет диагностику ведущего повреждающего агента. Функциональное состояние печени в процессе лечения в значительной степени определяется характером течения процесса, возникновением побочных реакций, а также функциональным состоянием печени до начала лечения [7,10].

Мнения авторов по вопросу потенциальной гепатотоксичности противотуберкулезных препаратов расходятся. Клинические проявления гепатотоксического действия отмечаются у 11-35% больных [8,11,6].

Необходимо отметить, что состояние печени у больного туберкулезом зависит от состояния макроорганизма, его реактивности. Изучение этой проблемы с

генетических подходов представляется перспективным, так как позволяет раскрывать патогенетические механизмы, способствующие прогрессированию основного процесса и развитию лекарственных осложнений от химиотерапии [3,2].

Цель: изучение частоты и характера поражения печени у больных туберкулезом легких с разным генетическим фоном.

Материал и методы. Проведено наблюдение и комплексное обследование 337 больных туберкулезом легких, находившихся на лечении в терапевтических отделениях клиники центра фтизиатрии и пульмонологии.

Среди обследованных мужчин - 171 (50,8%), женщин – 156 (49,2%).

Инфильтративный деструктивный туберкулез легких установлен у 216 (64,1±2,6%) больных; фиброзно-кавернозный - у 52 (15,4±1,9%); кавернозный - у 22 (6,5±1,8%); диссеминированный туберкулез легких – у 24 (7,2±1,4%); казеозная пневмония - у 23 (6,8±1,3%) больных. Среди обследованных больных впервые выявленные составили 87,8±1,7%; ранее леченные - 12,2±1,7%. Определяли следующие генетические маркеры:

-фенотип гаптоглобина методом дискэлектрофореза сыворотки крови в полиакриламидном геле по D.C.Davis в модификации Н.А.Осиной; выделяли фенотипы Нр 1-1, 2-1, 2-2; тип инактивации ГИНК в моче по Л.П.Гребеннику; активность эритроцитарной глюкозо-6-фосфатдегидрогеназы по А.Kornberg , норма- $120-180 \cdot 10^9$ эритроцитов в сыворотке крови [1]

Согласно К.С.Казакову с соавт. были выделены 4 комбинации генетических маркеров: неблагоприятная (НКГМ - носительство Нр 2-2+слабый тип инактивации ГИНК + пониженная активность Г-6-ФДГ), относительно неблагоприятная (ОНКГМ - сочетание двух неблагоприятных и одного благоприятного генетического маркера); благоприятная (БКГМ - носительство Нр 2-1+ сильный тип инактивации ГИНК + нормальная активность Г-6-ФДГ) и относительно благоприятная (ОБКГМ - сочетание двух благоприятных и одного неблагоприятного генетического маркера) [10].

Для оценки функционального состояния печени у больных ТЛ определяли активность ферментов крови и мочи: аспартатамино-трансфераза (АсТ) ($N = 0,43 \pm 0,05$ ммоль/ч.л.), аланинаминотрансферазы (АлТ) ($N = 0,20 \pm 0,03$ ммоль/ч.л.), по методу S.Rautman – S.Frenkel (1957), холинэстеразы (ХЭ) по методу В.Г.Колба ($N = 74,98 \pm 10,15$ мкм/ч.л), содержание общего билирубина по методу Йендрашека ($N = 7,4 \pm 0,25$ мкмоль/л). Определяли коэффициент Де Ритиса (соотношение АсТ к АлТ – $N = 2,15$) и билирубиновый показатель (соотношение прямого и общего билирубина – $N = 36\%$) [1]

Результаты и обсуждение. При обследовании 337 стационарных больных патология со стороны печени выявлена у 94 ($27,8 \pm 2,4\%$) пациентов.

При исследовании частоты и характера поражений печени у лиц с разными комбинациями генетических маркеров обращает на себя внимание, что у 7 ($21,2 \pm 7,1\%$) больных с НКГМ было поражение печени по типу токсического гепатита. В то же время у больных с БКГМ и ОБКГМ токсический гепатит отмечался в 2-3 раза реже – соответственно в $11,5 \pm 6,2$ и $6,8 \pm 3,4\%$ случаев. Вирусный гепатит в анамнезе выявлен у $27,2\%$ больных с НКГМ, у $3,8,0\%$ - с БКГМ, у $14,7\%$ - с ОНКГМ и у $9,1\%$ - ОБКГМ.

При обследовании на первый план выступают жалобы пациентов, объективно связанные с поражением печени, проявляющееся диспепсическим синдромом. Для диспепсической симптоматики у больных ДТЛ была характерна горечь во рту: при НКГМ – 36% , при БКГМ в 3 раза реже – $11,5\%$. У лиц с ОНКГМ и ОБКГМ данный симптом встречался в 2 раза реже, чем при НКГМ. Тошнота наиболее часто отмечалась у лиц с НКГМ – $51,5\%$ случаев, в 1,5-2 раза она была реже у больных с ОБКГМ и ОНКГМ и только у одного больного ($3,8\%$) с БКГМ. На ощущение чувства сдавления, тяжесть в правом подреберье жаловались $36,3\%$ больных с НКГМ, в 2 раза реже больные с БКГМ - $19,2\%$. При ОНКГМ и ОБКГМ этот симптом встречался только у $17,8$ и $15,9\%$ больных.

Рвота чаще наблюдалась у лиц с НКГМ – $30,3\%$, очень редко - у пациентов с ОНКГМ и ОБКГМ - соответственно $3,1$ и $3,4\%$ и не встречалась при БКГМ.

Зуд и сыпь на коже как проявление холестаза были у 30,3% больных с НКГМ, несколько реже при ОНКГМ и ОБКГМ – в 14,7% случаев. Боли в правом подреберье достоверно часто встречались у больных с НКГМ – 18,1% и не выявлены у пациентов с БКГМ. У больных с ОНКГМ и ОБКГМ частота данного симптома была невысокой – соответственно 5,7 и 3,4% случаев. Метеоризм был более характерным для больных с НКГМ (45,4%) при других комбинациях генетических маркеров встречался значительно реже.

Функциональные изменения со стороны печени выявлены у 123 (36,5±2,6%) обследованных. В 2 раза чаще они отмечались у больных с НКГМ: 48,4±3,6%, а при БКГМ только у 23,1±8,6% ($P < 0,05$). У больных с ОНКГМ и ОБКГМ эти изменения имели место в 39,4±3,5 и 29,5±4,8% случаев ($P > 0,05$).

У 48,4±3,6% больных ТЛ с НКГМ и у 53,8±4,2% с ОНКГМ отмечалось повышение активности в 1,3-3 раза индикаторных ферментов печени - АлТ и АсТ и снижение уровня ХЭ. Особенно выраженная ферментемия наблюдалась при фиброзно-кавернозном туберкулезе легких и казеозной пневмонии. В то же время у больных ТЛ с БКГМ (23,1±8,6%) и ОБКГМ (15,9±3,8%) активность АлТ и АсТ увеличивалась только в 1,3-1,8 раза.

Таким образом, как показали наши исследования, повышение активности АлТ и АсТ у больных ТЛ наблюдалось при НКГМ и ОНКГМ. У этих больных, особенно при фиброзно-кавернозном туберкулезе и казеозной пневмонии, активность изучаемых ферментов возрастала в 2,0-3,9 раза, что, видимо, было связано с токсическим поражением печени, наличием воспалительно-некротического компонента.

Коэффициент Де Ритиса у всех больных ТЛ, особенно с неблагоприятным генетическим фоном, был меньше 1,0, билирубиновый показатель также не превышал 50%, что указывает на наличие нарушения на уровне мембраны гепатоцитов.

Вывод. Учитывая наличие функциональных изменений на метаболическом – клеточном уровне, в комплексную терапию, особенно у больных ТЛ,

носителей НКГМ и ОНКГМ, в обязательном порядке нужно включить гепатопротекторные препараты.

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Лапароскопический адгезиолизис в хирургии острой спаечной кишечной непроходимости

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Цель исследования: улучшить результаты лечения больных острой спаечной кишечной (ОСКН) непроходимости путем обоснования целесообразности выполнения лапароскопического адгезиолизиса.

Материал и методы исследования: Нами были изучены результаты лечения 28 больных с ОСКН, находившихся на стационарном лечении с отделение экстренной хирургии многопрофильной клиники ТМА за период с 2015 по 2021 годы, которым была предпринята попытка выполнения лапароскопического адгезиолизиса. Из них 17 пациентов в анамнезе перенесли аппендэктомию, 3 оперированы по поводу гинекологической патологии, 4 больных были подвергнуты хирургическому вмешательству по поводу грыж живота, 2 перенесли в анамнезе открытую холецистэктомию и 2 пациента оперированы по поводу эхинококка печени.

Полученные результаты. На основании имеющегося клинического опыта выполнения открытых и лапароскопических вмешательств, мы определили круг клинических ситуаций, когда возможно выполнение лапароскопического адгезиолизиса. Показаниями были наличие нежного послеоперационного рубца, ранний срок заболевания, перенесенные в анамнезе не более двух операций в одной анатомической области брюшной полости или одной операции на нескольких анатомических областях, есвыраженное вздутие живота, наличие на рентгенограмме пневматоза кишечника или 2-3 тонкокишечных "арок" и чаш Клойбера.

При лапароскопическом адгезиолизе первый троакар устанавливали по методике Хассона для профилактики случайных перфораций кишечника. Дилатированные петли кишечника отодвигаются, затем необходимо обнаружить сдавленный спаечным тяжом сегмент тонкой кишки. Рассечение спаек выполняли путем биполярной коагуляции. Лапароскопическое разделение спаек выполняли в случаях, если интраоперационная картина

позволяло уверенно дифференцировать зону странгуляции кишки.

В 26 наблюдениях удалось операцию завершить лапароскопическим способом, лишь в 2 случаях у больных после перенесенной эхинококкэктомии пришлось прибегнуть к конверсии.

Заключение. Лапароскопический адгезиолиз возможно выполнять при достаточной квалификации хирурга у отобранных пациентов. Выполнение эффективного подбора больных с ОСКН необходимо для того, чтобы избежать увеличения осложнений. При подборе больных к лапароскопическому адгезиолизису необходимо учитывать следующие обстоятельства: количество и вид предыдущих лапаротомий; предшествующее хирургическое лечение, вызвавшее спаечный процесс; степень адгезивного синдрома; время от начала появления симптомов заболевания; степень расширения кишечника при рентгенологических исследованиях; тяжесть сопутствующих заболеваний и гемодинамического состояния.

Parotitis

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Abstract: Epidemic parotitis (lat. Parotitis epidemica, fever disease) is an acute infectious disease caused by a paramyxovirus characterized by non-purulent damage to the glands (salivary glands, pancreas, testicles) and the central nervous system.

The name “epidemic parotitis” is considered obsolete. Currently, the disease is often called “parotitis”. In Latin, salivary glands near the ear are called glandula parotidea, and its inflammation is parotitis; hence the name of the disease. Children between 3 and 15 years of age are most often diagnosed with measles.

Goiter (swelling of the glands) is transmitted by airborne droplets from an infected patient 9 days before and 5-9 days after the onset of symptoms.

The causative agent of mumps is an RNA-storing virus belonging to the family Paramyxoviruses (Paramyxoviridae), genus Rubulavirus. The pathogen was isolated and studied in 1934 by E. Gudpacher and K. Johnson.

After experiencing mumps, a person often develops a stable lifelong immunity, but relapses also occur.

Incubation period (the time interval from infection to the development of disease symptoms) is 11-23 days; often – 13-19 days. In some people, prodromal events are observed 1-2 days before (weakness, restlessness, muscle pain, headache, fever, appetite and sleep disorders). With the development of the disease, the symptoms become worse, the symptoms of damage to the salivary glands are noticed: dry mouth; pain around the ear that increases during chewing and talking.

5. Manifest forms

Uncomplicated: only damage to the salivary glands (one or more);

Complicated: damage to salivary glands and other organs (meningitis, meningoencephalitis, pancreatitis, orchitis, mastitis, myocarditis, arthritis, nephritis).

Depending on the severity of the transition:

Mild (including dim and atypical forms): subfebrile fever, without symptoms of intoxication or with weak symptoms, without complications.

Moderate: febrile fever (38-39.9 °C), high body temperature persists for a long time, and signs of general intoxication (with fever, headache, arthralgia and myalgia) are noticeable, so significant enlargement of the lacrimal glands – often bilateral parotitis, complications are noted.

Severe: a very high rise in body temperature (40 °C and above), its long-term preservation (up to 2 weeks or more), sharply expressed signs of general intoxication (asthenia, severe weakness, tachycardia, with a decrease in blood pressure, sleep disorders, anorexia, etc.).

Fever reaches its maximum level in 1-2 days and lasts for 4-7 days. The area of the damaged salivary glands will be painful. The pain is expressed in several points: in front of the ear, behind the ear (Filatov's sign) and in the area of the mastoid tumor. Mursu's symptom is an inflammatory reaction of the mucous membrane in the area of the salivary duct near the damaged ear. The skin on it becomes tight, shiny, swelling can spread to the neck. The enlargement of the glands reaches its maximum level in 3 days, remains for 2-3 days and gradually (in 7-10 days) begins to return to normal.

Epidemic parotitis has a good prognosis, and the mortality rate is very low (1 in 100,000 cases), but the risk of testicular atrophy (leading to infertility) and deafness must be taken into account.

Patients with diabetes can be treated at home. Hospitalization is carried out in case of serious complications and according to epidemiological guidelines. Patients are isolated at home for 9 days. A 21-day quarantine will be announced in children's institutions where measles has been detected.

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Low blood pressure

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Abstract: Low blood pressure, arterial hypotension, hypotonia (Greek ens – under, low and Latin tension – tension) – arterial pressure more than 20% of the initial / normal values or in absolute numbers – 90/60 mm sim. Above is said to fall from Decreased blood pressure can be acute or chronic.

As a rule, acute arterial hypotension (collapse, shock) occurs with heart failure, large blood loss, dehydration and quickly leads to hypoxia of the brain and internal organs. Thus, acute hypotension is always a complication of certain diseases or external influences, and there are always clear reasons that should be taken into account in treatment.

Unlike its acute form, chronic arterial hypotension is generally caused by other reasons. In people with low blood pressure, its regulation is usually disturbed, and the real reasons are of different nature.

Patients with low blood pressure do not have the risk of heart attack and stroke that are high in those with high blood pressure, therefore, standards and methods for the treatment of chronic hypotension are not yet well developed. At the same time, the quality of life of hypotensives (patients suffering from low blood pressure) can be very low due to constant weakness, headaches, decreased activity and other symptoms.

The following types of arterial hypotension are distinguished:

Acute hypotension;

Chronic arterial hypotension:

Primary chronic arterial hypotension;

Secondary chronic arterial hypotension;

Acute symptomatic hypotension (sudden drop in blood pressure). For example, acute myocardial infarction, pulmonary artery embolism, severe arrhythmias,

intracardiac blockades, allergic reactions, blood loss, etc. are accompanied by very low blood pressure. Such a situation requires urgent medical attention.

Physiological (chronic) hypotonia is observed in well-trained athletes and in cases of genetic predisposition to low blood pressure that does not exceed the norm.

Primary (idiopathic or essential) hypotension is an independent disease. According to one of the theories, primary hypotonia is a special form of neurosis-like disease of the vasomotor centers of the brain, and long-term psychoemotional tension and stress can play a big role in its development.

Secondary arterial hypotonia is caused by other diseases (for example, osteochondrosis of the cervical spine, peptic ulcer, anemia, hepatitis, pancreatitis, cystitis, tuberculosis, rheumatism), arrhythmia, alcoholism, diabetes, diseases of the endocrine system or respiratory system, tumors, shock, brain injuries, cirrhosis of the liver, mental trauma, circulatory disorders, heart failure, intoxication, side effects of some drugs (for example, their overdosage in the treatment of hypertension), etc. Low blood pressure can develop due to starvation and lack of vitamins E, C, B and pantothenic acid (B5).

Hypotonia is also observed in healthy people, for example, in athletes engaged in constant physical activity. This is called “hypotonia of activity”. In this case, lowering blood pressure serves as the body’s defense mechanism. It can be seen that when there is constant tension, the body starts to work in an “economical” mode, the heart rate decreases and blood pressure decreases.

A healthy lifestyle is the best way to prevent low blood pressure. This means eating rationally, exercising, resting, and taking vascular strengthening treatments (massage, contrast shower, hydro massage, swimming).

Avoid stress. It is important to enjoy life, to feel needed and indispensable in life and family. For hypotonics, negative emotions often become a factor that causes a sharp and strong drop in blood pressure.

It is recommended to independently monitor the level of blood pressure and undergo regular preventive examinations with a cardiologist. The doctor can prescribe drugs (adaptogens, alpha-adrenomimetics, and analeptics) to raise blood pressure.

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General blood analysis

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Abstract: General blood analysis is a laboratory test used to obtain information about the physical and chemical properties of blood. A blood test is usually performed on a capillary blood sample taken from a finger or an ear. In some cases, bone marrow blood cells may also be tested. In our time, hundreds of hematological tests and procedures have been developed, and with the help of an automatizer, it is possible to perform different blood tests on the same blood sample at the same time. Blood consists of plasma and blood cells (formed elements). Blood cells consist of erythrocytes (red blood cells), leukocytes and platelets. Blood plasma is a transparent liquid that makes up more than half of blood volume (55-60%). A centrifuge is used to separate the blood plasma from the shaped elements.

Many tests are designed to determine the number of erythrocytes and leukocytes in the blood, as well as the erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and the concentration of hemoglobin in erythrocytes. In addition, some blood tests are used to determine Rhesus factors, Rh or blood groups. In other cases, the shape and structural details of blood cells, hemoglobin and other blood proteins are determined. Blood can be analyzed to determine the activity of various enzymes or protein catalysts associated with blood cells or found in blood plasma.

Blood can be further analyzed based on total volume, circulation time, viscosity, coagulation and clotting disorders, acidic medium (pH), oxygen and carbon dioxide content, and clearance properties of various substances. There are special serological tests for the detection of substances specific to specific infections, such as syphilis, hepatitis, and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV, AIDS).

Hemoglobin (Hb) is a protein that can bind and transport oxygen and contains an iron atom. Hemoglobin is in red blood cells (erythrocytes). Hemoglobin content is measured in grams/liter (gr/l). It is very important to determine the amount of

hemoglobin, because a decrease in its amount leads to a lack of oxygen to the tissues and organs of the whole body.

REDUCTION OF HEMOGLOBIN (DEFICIENCY) - CAUSES

Anemia

Leukemia

Congenital blood diseases (sickle cell anemia, thalassemia)

Iron deficiency

Lack of vitamins

Blood loss

CAUSES OF INCREASED HEMOGLOBIN

Dehydration (decreased fluid in the body (thirst), excessive sweating, reduced kidney function, diabetes, diabetes insipidus, excessive vomiting or diarrhea, use of diuretics)

Congenital heart and lung defects

Lung failure or heart failure

Kidney disease (renal artery stenosis, benign kidney tumors)

Diseases of hematopoiesis (production of blood-forming elements) (erythremia)

Erythrocytes are small red blood cells. These are the largest number of blood cells.

Their main task is to transport oxygen and deliver it to organs and tissues.

Erythrocytes are in the form of concave discs on both sides. Erythrocytes contain a large amount of hemoglobin - they occupy a large part of the red disc.

A decrease in the number of red blood cells is called anemia. There are many reasons for the development of this condition, and they are not always related to the hematopoietic system.

Nutritional errors (food lacking in vitamins and proteins)

Blood loss

Leukemia (white blood disease)

Hereditary enzymeopathy (defects of enzymes involved in hematopoiesis)

Hemolysis (death of blood cells due to exposure to toxic substances and autoimmune diseases)

Dehydration (vomiting, diarrhea, excessive sweating, low fluid intake)

Erythremia (hematopoietic system diseases)

Diseases of the cardiovascular or respiratory system that cause breathing and heart failure

Renal artery stenosis

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Avian influenza

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Abstract: Avian influenza is a viral infectious disease of birds; some strains of the virus are pathogenic for humans and is a severe disease with high mortality. Bird flu is accompanied by fever, diarrhea, vomiting, catarrhal syndrome, bleeding from the nose and gums, chest pain, pneumonia, acute shortness of breath, and pulmonary edema. Research methods such as IFA, PCR, virological studies, chest X-ray are used to confirm the diagnosis of bird flu. Treatment of bird flu includes hospitalization of the patient, appointment of antiviral and symptomatic agents.

Avian influenza is an acute viral disease, accompanied by infectious-toxic, gastrointestinal and respiratory syndrome in humans. Human infection with the bird flu virus was first known in 1997 during an epidemic in Hong Kong. In the following years, bird flu spread from Asia to Europe and Africa, infecting millions of wild and domestic birds and causing illness among hundreds of people. The urgency of the fight against bird flu is related to the forced killing of birds, as well as high economic losses due to the fact that the disease has a pandemic potential among the population. Avian influenza has an extremely aggressive course: mortality rates due to lung complications reach 60-70%.

The RNA virus that causes avian influenza belongs to the family Orthomyxoviridae, type A influenza viruses. Depending on the type of proteins (hemagglutinin and neuraminidase) in its shell, different antigen types of bird flu are distinguished. The most dangerous for humans are the H5N1 and H7N7 strains, which mutate quickly. The severe form of the disease develops at lightning speed and can lead to high mortality. These strains are especially dangerous in combination with seasonal and swine flu viruses. There have also been cases of bird flu caused by the low-pathogenic H7N9 virus, mainly in patients with other diseases. The bird flu virus can survive for a long time at low temperatures, but it dies after 2-3 minutes when boiled.

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF BIRD FLU

In the initial period of the disease, the symptoms of bird flu are similar to normal seasonal flu, which complicates the diagnosis. In addition, it is necessary to distinguish avian influenza from parainfluenza, adenovirus, rhinovirus, respiratory syndical infection. The main criteria for diagnosing bird flu are the presence of an epidemic in the region, contact with infected birds, high fever, diarrhea, and observation of progressive pneumonia. X-ray of the chest reveals many inflammatory infiltrates that can unite and quickly spread in the lung tissue in the early stages of the disease. Confirmation of avian influenza is carried out by immunological (IFA), molecular genetic (PCR), virological methods.

Patients with suspected or confirmed bird flu are admitted to infectious inpatients. Etiotropic treatment of the disease is carried out using antiviral drugs that reduce virus replication and improve survival prospects. The most effective among them are Oseltamivir, Zanamivir, Rimantadine and Ufifenovir. Antipyretic drugs (paracetamol, ibuprofen) are given for high fever. The use of acetylsalicylic acid (Aspirin) and metamizole sodium in the treatment of bird flu is strictly prohibited. When bacterial complications develop, antibacterial drugs are given.

Immunity after bird flu is short-lived and species-specific. This means that there is a possibility of getting sick again in another season. The death rate of infectious diseases caused by the most pathogenic strains of bird flu is 50-70%. According to the worst estimates, the A virus (H5N1) could cause a worldwide bird flu pandemic and cause the death of 150 million people.

Birds infected with avian influenza virus are culled. Poultry vaccination is used as a means of controlling infectious epizootics. Prevention of bird flu in humans is aimed at strengthening the immune system, using antiviral drugs according to the preventive procedure. If possible, it is necessary to avoid close contact with domestic and wild birds, and to take precautions when preparing poultry meat and chicken eggs. The flu vaccine can reduce the risk of complications, as well as the potential mutation and person-to-person transmission of the avian influenza virus.

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An allergy

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Abstract: An allergy is a response of the immune system to substances that affect or come into contact with the body, such as animal dander, dust, or bee venom.

The substance that causes an allergic reaction is called “allergen”. Allergens are present in food, drink and environment. Most allergens are harmless, that is, in most people, these substances do not cause allergies.

Allergies are very common. According to health authorities, approximately 20% of people in North America and Western Europe are affected by pollinosis (allergic rhino conjunctivitis, allergic rhinitis).

All over the world, the number of people suffering from allergies is increasing. According to Allergy UK, around 30-40% of people will experience allergies at some point in their lives. Allergies are most common in children, especially food allergies.

If an allergic person encounters an allergen, an allergic reaction does not occur immediately. The immune system gradually becomes more sensitive to the substance.

Over time, the body becomes more sensitive – this process is called sensitization. Sensitization can last from several days to several years. In most cases, the sensitization process is not completed and the patient has some symptoms, but not a full allergic reaction.

When the immune system reacts to an allergen, inflammation and irritation appear. Signs and symptoms depend on the type of allergen. Allergic reactions can occur in the intestines (digestive system), skin, sinuses, airways, eyes and nasal passages.

Symptoms of allergy to dust and dust mites have the following symptoms:

Runny nose;

Itching of the eyes;

Itching in the nose;

Rhinitis;

Swelling of the eyes;

Watery eyes;

Coughing.

Symptoms of skin allergies, such as eczema (atopic dermatitis):

Skin shedding;

Itching;

Skin dryness;

Red rashes on the skin.

Allergies to food products (food) have different reactions:

Return;

Swelling of the tongue;

Soreness in the mouth;

Swelling of the lip;

Swelling of the face;

Swelling of the throat;

Stomach spasm;

Respiratory disorders;

Rectal bleeding (rarely in children);

Diarrhea;

Anaphylaxis (anaphylactic shock) is a very serious, often life-threatening allergic reaction.

The human immune system responds to an allergen as a pathogen (external harmful substance) and tries to destroy it, like a foreign bacteria, virus, fungus or toxin.

However, the allergen is not harmful. It is just that the immune system has become very sensitive to this substance.

When the immune system reacts to an allergy, it releases immunoglobulin E (IgE), a type of antibody, to destroy the allergen. It produces chemicals in the body that cause an allergic reaction.

One of these chemicals is called histamine. Histamine causes muscle contractions, including those in the walls of blood vessels and airways. Histamine also helps clear mucus from the nose.

An allergy sufferer blames allergy symptoms on an allergen—a friend’s pet, plant dust, or dust. However, they are wrong. The problem is not the allergen, but the allergic person’s immune system.

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Tachycardia

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Abstract: Tachycardia, rapid heartbeat (from Greek tachýs- fast and kardia - heart) is an increase in the number of heart contractions (HR) more than 90 times per minute. Two forms of tachycardia should be distinguished:

pathological, that is, an increase in heart rate at rest;

Physiological - an increase in ESR as a result of physical stress, excitement or fear is considered normal.

Tachycardia is not a disease, but a symptom, as it can be observed as a manifestation of many diseases. Its most common causes are disorders of the autonomic nervous system, diseases of the endocrine system, hemodynamic disorders, and various forms of arrhythmia.

Pathological tachycardia can cause negative consequences:

First, when the heart beats fast, its efficiency decreases, because the ventricles do not have time to fill with blood, as a result, blood pressure decreases and the quality of its delivery to the organs deteriorates.

Secondly, the heart's own blood supply is also impaired, because it does more work per unit of time and, accordingly, requires more oxygen, its poor blood supply increases the risk of coronary heart disease and subsequent heart attacks.

CLINIC

An attack develops suddenly, heart activity changes to another rhythm. The number of heart contractions in the ventricular form usually reaches 150-180 pulses per minute, in the supraventricular form - up to 180-240 pulses. Often, during an attack, the jugular veins pulsate.

On auscultation, a pendulum-like rhythm (embryo cardia) is characteristic, no difference between I and II tone is noticeable. The duration of an attack can last from a few seconds to several days. Nodular and compartmental paroxysmal tachycardia does not significantly affect central hemodynamics.

However, heart failure may worsen and swelling may increase in patients with IHF. Supraventricular paroxysmal tachycardia increases myocardial oxygen demand and can lead to an attack of acute coronary insufficiency. Characteristically, the sinusoidal form does not start suddenly and, in the same way, gradually ends.

Treatment of ventricular tachycardia requires the use of antiarrhythmic drugs, treatment of the primary disease, and measures to eliminate factors that cause arrhythmia (glycoside intoxication, electrolyte disturbances, and hypoxemia).

The main antiarrhythmic agent used in the treatment is lidocaine, which is injected intravenously in a dose of 1 mg per 1 kg of the patient's weight (average 70-100 mg) in a few minutes. If there is no effect, after 10-15 minutes, the drug is injected again in the same dose. In recurrent tachycardia, lidocaine is administered intravenously at a dose of 1-2 mg per minute for 24-48 hours.

If ventricular tachycardia is accompanied by a drop in blood pressure, blood pressure should be increased to 100-110 mmHg by intravenous noradrenaline or other pressor amines. Failure to observe the effect serves as an indication for the use of electro impulse therapy.

In cases where lidocaine fails to stop ventricular tachycardia, Novocain amide, aymalin, β -blockers are used.

In the treatment of patients with ventricular tachycardia caused by cardiac glycoside intoxication, potassium chloride and lidocaine are administered intravenously or by slow-flow oral administration.

The prognosis of patients with ventricular tachycardia is negative, as it is a manifestation of severe myocardial damage in most of them. Among patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, heart failure, and hypotension, the death rate is especially high.

Tachycardia is also treated with minimally invasive surgery - under local anesthesia, without leaving stitches. It can be radiofrequency catheter ablation, artificial pacemaker installation, etc.

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Congenital heart defect

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Abstract: Congenital heart disease (CPH) is a defect in the structure of the heart and (or) large vessels, which is present in the patient from birth. Most cancers disrupt the flow of blood within the heart or within the major and minor circulations. Heart defects are the most common birth defects and the leading cause of death in children due to developmental defects.

What is congenital heart disease? Among newborns, the incidence of congenital heart disease is 1% (one in 100 babies). The occurrence rate of TYP is second only to congenital malformations of the nervous system.

Congenital heart disease can be caused by genetic (heredity) or environmental (environmental) factors, but usually a combination of the two.

The most studied causes of congenital heart disease are point mutations or chromosomal mutations in the form of deletions or duplications of DNA segments. Major chromosomal abnormalities such as trisomy 21, 13, and 18 account for approximately 5–8% of TYP cases. Trisomy 21 is the most common genetic cause. Some genes are associated with certain diseases. Mutations of the cardiac muscle protein α -myosin heavy chain (MYH6) are associated with intercompartmental barrier defects.

Genetic mutations are caused by the action of three main mutagens:

Physical mutagens are mainly ionizing radiation.

Chemical mutagens - lacquers, dyes, phenols, nitrates, benzpyrene in tobacco smoking, alcohol consumption, hydantoin, lithium, thalidomide, teratogenic drugs - antibiotics and HTP, NYQP, etc.).

Biological mutagens - mainly the presence of the rubella virus in the mother's body, which causes congenital rubella in the fetus and the characteristic Gregg's triad - congenital heart defects, cataracts and deafness; Also, the presence of systemic lupus

erythematosis, diabetes, phenylketonuria in the mother can also serve as a biological mutagen.

CLASSIFICATION

There are many classifications of birth defects. Congenital heart disease is conditionally divided into 2 groups:

1. White (arterial and venous blood do not mix, with left-right flow of blood). It includes four groups:

With enrichment of the small blood circulation circle (open arterial tube, intercompartmental barrier defect, interventricular barrier defect, AB-communication, etc.);

With weakening of the small circulatory circle (isolated pulmonary stenosis, etc.);

With weakening of the circle of large blood circulation (isolated aortic stenosis, coarctation of the aorta, etc.);

Without a significant disturbance of systemic hemodynamics (dispositions of the heart - dextro-, sinistro-, mesocardia, heart dystopia - neck, chest, ventral).

2. Blue (with right-left flow of blood, mixing arterial and venous blood). Includes two groups:

With enrichment of the small blood circulation circle (complete transposition of the trunk vessels, Eisenmenger complex, etc.).

With weakening of the small circle of rotation (tetrad of Fallot, Ebstein's anomaly, etc.).

In 2000, the International Nomenclature was developed to create a general classification system for birth defects.

CONSEQUENCE

It is relatively good if it is detected early and there is a possibility of radical treatment. If there is no such possibility, the outcome is doubtful or bad.

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Surgical treatment of radicular cysts with the use of Biocomposite material

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Relevance of the topic: In the outpatient practice of surgical dentistry, radicular cysts account for 78-96% of the total number of cysts and 7-12% of the total number of jaw diseases. These figures indicate the relevance of the problem of treatment of this pathology. The priority tasks of surgical treatment of patients with radicular cysts are the restoration of the bone tissue structure and the preservation of tooth function. The main method of surgical treatment remains cystectomy with resection of the root apex. The disadvantages of the Parch-II cystectomy technique include decreased function of the teeth located in the area of the cyst, reinfection, and residual bone cavities that reduce bone strength. Violation of the integrity of the bone in the area of surgical intervention is often associated with prolonged healing, the outcome of which is incomplete or incomplete restoration of bone tissue.

Improving the methods of surgical treatment of radicular cysts can lead to a significant reduction in indications for the removal of causative teeth. One of the solutions to this problem is the filling of residual cystic cavities with osteoplastic materials. Their active use implies a reduction in the postoperative period, strengthening the teeth involved in the cystic process, reducing complications and accelerating bone maturation. But the experience of clinical observations has shown the low efficiency of some materials, especially with significant bone defects, since they are not always completely replaced by bone, but are encapsulated by connective tissue, maintain chronic inflammation, enhance bone resorption, or are partially rejected.

In this regard, the choice of a treatment method that would use materials that meet modern requirements is of particular importance. Osteoplastic preparations should have such parameters as the absence of toxicity, bacterial and viral safety, complete biodegradability, biocompatibility, a combination of osteoconductive and osteoinductive properties.

One of the directions in bone reconstruction surgery is the use of platelet-rich plasma, which has a combined reparative effect on hard and soft tissues due to the

activated platelets with growth factors, fibrin and leukocytes contained in it and does not cause toxic or immune reactions.

The peculiarity of the use of osteogenesis optimization means is that they show their positive qualities at certain stages of bone restoration. Therefore, the combined use of biocomposite osteoplastic materials and platelet-rich autoplasm suggests the creation of optimal conditions for bone formation by reducing the inflammatory response of tissues and effectively influencing the mechanisms of ossification.

Literature data on the joint use of platelet-rich plasma with bone grafting materials is not enough. Based on the foregoing, it seems necessary and relevant to develop a method with a predictable result for the surgical treatment of patients with radicular cysts. To optimize reparative processes, the combined use of platelet-rich plasma and biocomposite material Kollapan-L is promising.

Purpose of the study: Optimization of surgical treatment of radicular cysts by using a biocomposite material and platelet-rich fibrin to fill a postoperative bone defect.

Research methods:

1. Clinical examination of patients.
2. Experimental study
3. X-ray studies.

Research objectives:

1. To study in an experiment on laboratory animals the osteoplastic properties of the biocomposite material "Kollapan-L" and fibrin enriched with platelets.
2. Conduct a thermometric analysis of the course of the early postoperative period in patients with radicular cysts in the study groups.
3. To determine the dynamics of bone tissue recovery in patients with radicular cysts after cystectomy using the biocomposite material "Kollapan-L" and fibrin enriched with platelets using ultrasonic osteometry, radiography, digital densitometry.
4. Evaluate the results of using the Kollapan-L complex and platelet-rich fibrin after surgical treatment of patients with radicular cysts.

Scientific novelty. We will introduce into clinical practice a complex method of surgical treatment of patients with radicular cysts using Kollapan-L as an osteoplastic material in combination with platelet-enriched fibrin gel, which is an autogenous source of growth factors. We prove its clinical effectiveness, an objective assessment is given as a method of choice in the surgical treatment of radicular cysts. The actions of "Kollapan-L" and fibrin gel enriched with platelets, when filling a postoperative bone defect of the jaws, will be proved in the experiment and in the course of clinical studies.

Let us substantiate the need for cystectomy in the jaw area without resection of the apices of the roots of the teeth with their coating with a PKR membrane (platelet-rich fibrin), which significantly reduces the trauma of the operation.

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Jaundice

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Abstract: Jaundice (lat. icterus) is a yellow tint of the skin and visible mucous membranes, which occurs as a result of an increase in the amount of bilirubin in the blood and tissues. Most people understand this term as hepatitis A or Botkin's disease. In fact, this word is used to refer to a number of pathological changes affecting not only the liver, but also other organs. Nevertheless, jaundice is always associated with a violation of bilirubin metabolism, which can occur for various reasons.

Jaundice is a set of symptoms, as a result of increased bilirubin, the skin, sclera of the eyes, and mucous membranes become yellowish. Normally, bilirubin is released during the breakdown of erythrocytes in the spleen. Then it goes to the liver and after participating in metabolic processes, it leaves the body.

If there is a violation in any of the above stages, the compound bilirubin accumulates in the blood, causing the sclera and mucous membranes to turn yellow. Why does this happen? During the breakdown of hemoglobin, a yellow pigment is formed in the body. Normally, it leaves the body during defecation. A lot of bilirubin remains in the blood during the development of jaundice, which is accompanied by liver failure and impaired bile duct permeability. In this case, a small amount of this substance is excreted through the skin or kidneys.

This disease is one of the most common. Yellow disease is especially common in countries with hot climates and poor sanitary conditions. For example, in Central Asia, almost every child experiences this disease. The prevalence of viral disease in Eastern Europe is 250 per 100,000 population per year.

Jaundice is often referred to as "hepatitis A" or "Botkin's disease". This viral pathology is accompanied by general intoxication of the body and liver dysfunction. In addition, there are viral hepatitis B and hepatitis C, as well as autoimmune, mononucleosis, toxic, bacterial, medicinal forms of the disease.

In the development of jaundice, the incubation period can be extended to several months. Depending on the duration of the disease, it can be acute, long-term or chronic.

Common symptoms of the disease in adults include:

Yellowing of the skin;

Enlargement of the liver and spleen;

An increase in erythrocytes in the blood;

The appearance of a venous network in the abdomen.

In adults, jaundice can be manifested by severe itching of the skin, changes in the color of urine and feces. Due to the high concentration of bilirubin in the body, feces are gray and urine is very dark. A person loses appetite and often feels significant pains of a spasmodic or pulling nature under the right rib.

Pathology treatment methods directly depend on its form and stage of development.

In order to ensure that the treatment is as effective as possible, it is necessary to determine the cause of the disease. In any case, conservative treatment can be prescribed to eliminate the symptoms of jaundice, and in severe cases, surgery is performed and it involves liver transplantation.

Conservative treatment consists of the following components:

Use of drugs — antihistamines, steroids.

Plasmapheresis.

Phototherapy.

Dieting.

The goal of treatment is to eliminate the virus, prevent liver cirrhosis, and reduce the risk of spreading the disease to others. If a person has developed a chronic autoimmune form of hepatitis, treatment with corticosteroids is prescribed.

Regardless of the type of jaundice, it is necessary to avoid alcohol, fatty and spicy foods - all this puts an additional burden on the weakened liver.

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Heart failure

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Abstract: Heart failure is an acute or chronic condition caused by weakening of the myocardial contractility and damping events within the large or small blood circulation. It is manifested by panting at rest or with some activity, rapid fatigue, swelling, cyanosis (bruising) of the nails and the lip-nasal triangle.

Acute heart failure is dangerous with the development of pulmonary edema and cardiogenic shock, and chronic heart failure leads to the development of organ hypoxia. Heart failure is one of the most common causes of human death.

In heart failure, a decrease in the contractile (pumping) function of the heart leads to an imbalance between the hemodynamic requirements of the body and the ability of the heart to meet this need. This imbalance is manifested by the superiority of the venous flow to the heart over the ability of the heart to transfer blood to the arterial system, and the resistance that the myocardium must overcome to drive blood into the veins.

Heart failure is not considered an independent heart disease and develops as a complication of various pathologies of the vessels and heart: valve defects of the heart, ischemic disease, cardiomyopathy, arterial hypertension, etc.

In some diseases (for example, arterial hypertension), the increase in the manifestation of heart failure gradually increases over the years, but in other cases (acute myocardial infarction), when a part of the functional cells dies, it is time is reduced to days and hours. In the acute development of heart failure (minutes, hours, days), we talk about its acute form. In other cases, heart failure is considered chronic. Among the most common causes of heart failure (in 60-70% of patients), myocardial infarction and MI are distinguished. They are followed by rheumatic heart diseases (14%) and dilated cardiomyopathy (11%). In the group over 60 years old, heart failure is also caused by hypertensive disease (4%). Type 2 diabetes mellitus and its

combination with arterial hypertension serve as a frequent cause of heart failure in elderly patients.

SYMPTOMS

SYMPTOMS OF ACUTE HEART FAILURE

It is caused by the weakening of the function of one part of the heart: the left ventricle or ventricle, the right ventricle. Acute left ventricular failure develops in diseases in which the load mainly falls on the left ventricle (hypertensive disease, aortic valve, myocardial infarction). When the functions of the left ventricle are weakened, the pressure in the pulmonary veins, arterioles and capillaries increases, their permeability increases, as a result of which the liquid part of the blood begins to leak, and as a result, interstitial and then alveolar edema develops. The initial stages of chronic heart failure can develop in left and right ventricular, left and right ventricular types. Aortic malformation, mitral valve insufficiency, arterial hypertension, coronary insufficiency develops damping in the vessels of the small circulatory circle and chronic left ventricular failure. It is characterized by vascular and gas exchange changes in the lungs. Shortness of breath, suffocation (usually at night), cyanosis, palpitations, cough (dry, sometimes with blood), rapid fatigue are observed.

Therapy is aimed at eliminating the primary cause (IHF, hypertension, rheumatism, myocarditis, etc.). In the presence of heart defects, cardiac aneurysm, adhesive pericarditis causing mechanical obstruction to the work of the heart, surgical intervention is often resorted to.

In acute or severe chronic heart failure, bed rest, complete mental and physical rest are prescribed. In other cases, it is necessary to follow an average load that does not worsen the situation. Liquid consumption is limited to 500-600 ml, salt - 1-2 g per day. It is prescribed to follow a diet rich in vitamins and easy to digest.

The five-year survival rate in patients is 50%. The subsequent prognosis is variable and is influenced by the severity of heart failure, accompanying pathologies, effectiveness of treatment, lifestyle, etc. Treatment of heart failure in the initial

stages fully covers the condition of patients; the worst outcome is observed in stage III heart failure.

As a preventive measure, it is necessary to take measures to prevent diseases that cause pathology (IHF, hypertension, heart defects, etc.) and factors that contribute to its occurrence. In order to prevent the worsening of the developed heart failure, it is necessary to optimize physical activity, take the prescribed drugs and be under the constant supervision of a cardiologist.

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